

RESEARCH REPORT ON CORRUPTION IN INDIA

India Corruption Research Report 2024 - ICRR 2024

An Editorial Initiative of Raman Media Network (RMN)

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Today, no government in India is willing to stop corruption because now it has become the lifeblood of Indian bureaucrats and politicians. All major global anti-corruption organizations observe that corruption has been increasing at an alarming pace in India while the government has no plans and procedures to stop corruption in the country.

Table of Contents

India Corruption Research Report 2024 (ICRR 2024)

No.	Topic	Page
1.	EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	3
2.	OPENING STATEMENT	4
3.	BUREAUCRATIC AND POLITICAL CORRUPTION	5
4.	OVERVIEW OF CORRUPTION IN INDIA	7
5.	ICRR 2024: KEY FACTS	11
6.	ABOUT INDIA CORRUPTION RESEARCH REPORT	12
7.	CORRUPTION PERCEPTION SURVEY	12
8.	GLOBAL OBSERVATIONS ON CORRUPTION IN INDIA	20
9.	COMPLICIT ANTI-CORRUPTION AGENCIES OF INDIA	21
10.	DELIBERATE NEGLIGENCE IN APPLYING ANTI-CORRUPTION LAWS	22
11.	ACTION TO REVAMP CORRUPTION PREVENTION PROCESSES	24
12.	WIDHOUSE CORRUPTION SCANDAL OF DELHI	26
13.	FORMS OF CORRUPTION AND ITS IMPACT	27
14.	CASE STUDIES OF GRAND CORRUPTION	28
15.	CLEAN HOUSE ANTI-CORRUPTION SERVICE	52
16.	UNTRAINED ANTI-CORRUPTION OFFICERS IN INDIA	54
17.	TECHNOLOGY INTERFACE TO TACKLE CORRUPTION	54
18.	10 RECOMMENDATIONS TO COMBAT CORRUPTION	60
19.	ABOUT THE EDITOR	62
20.	CIRCULATION OF INDIA CORRUPTION RESEARCH REPORT 2024	64

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

While India is already perceived to be one of the most corrupt countries in the world, bureaucratic and political corruption is still increasing dramatically in the country. However, there is no reliable official information available on the extent of corruption, as there is no attempt by the government to deal with corruption.

The India Corruption Research Report 2024 (ICRR 2024) is the third annual report while the first report ICRR 2022 was released in October 2022 and the second report ICRR 2023 was released in October 2023. This research report covers diverse aspects of corruption in India. The findings of the report will help the Central as well as State governments in the country make actionable strategies to combat

corruption.

The report will also enable other stakeholders including businesses, political parties, and international organizations to understand the perilous effects of corruption in India, which is still an underdeveloped country even after more than 75 years of its independence.

“Corruption robs schools, hospitals, and others of vitally needed funds. It rots institutions, as public officials enrich themselves or turn a blind eye to criminality. It deprives people of their rights, drives away foreign investment, and despoils the environment,” says UN Secretary General António Guterres. [Photo: UN]

The report aims to strengthen the anti-corruption efforts of the government agencies such as the Central Vigilance Commission (CVC), anti-corruption authority Lokpal, anti-corruption ombudsman organizations Lokayukta in different Indian States, the anti-corruption wing of the Central Bureau of Investigation (CBI), and other departments run by traditional bureaucrats. The India Corruption Research Report is the only reliable document which covers various aspects of corruption in India.

Among its other objectives, the report will provide necessary inputs to the business community including industry associations such as the Confederation of Indian Industry (CII), the Associated Chambers of Commerce and Industry of India (ASSOCHAM), the Federation of Indian Chambers of Commerce and Industry (FICCI), and foreign business associations that operate in India.

With its international coverage, the report will enable the global anti-corruption organizations particularly under the UN umbrella to understand the reasons and scope of corruption in India so that they could strategize their relationship with this poor country of nearly 1.4 billion people in order to focus on the achievement of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

The research report has been compiled and edited by Rakesh Raman who is a national award-winning journalist and founder of the humanitarian organization RMN Foundation. These days, he runs global news services on different subjects and publishes *The Integrity Bulletin* news magazine that covers local and international corruption news and issues.

He also runs various anti-corruption campaigns including an anti-corruption community court called *Clean House* to report about corruption cases that affect the people at large. Earlier, he had been associated with the United Nations (UN) through the United Nations Industrial Development Organization (UNIDO) as a digital media expert.

OPENING STATEMENT

As the corruption methods have always been evolving in India, the contemporary system of corruption has assumed the form of an organized trade in which corruption has become a non-issue in the country. Bribery is the traditional form of corruption, but now the acts of corruption are happening on a broader landscape. For example, massive political corruption in connivance with private corporations is taking place under the garb of secret electoral bonds.

Likewise, megalomaniac politicians such as the prime minister and the chief ministers in different Indian States splurge huge public funds to promote themselves through advertisements and publicity campaigns carried out in collusion with corrupt media outlets. While governance is a collaborative exercise, these corrupt politicians get their own photographs published on all publicity material to hoodwink the voters and get undue political advantage in elections.

The political parties also sell election tickets in crores of rupees secretly to candidates who want to contest elections under their banners. The ill-gotten money is spent by politicians to bribe the voters, purchase crowds who attend politicians' election rallies, and hire hoodlums who commit riots and spread violence before and during elections to help political parties win elections unscrupulously.

Similarly, the bureaucratic corruption style is also evolving. Now, bureaucrats circumvent the law and misuse their discretionary powers to give undue benefits to those who bribe them. Dereliction of duty, inefficiency, lack of skills to handle official work, ignorance, apathy toward citizens, reckless decisions to plunder public funds are also among the new forms of corruption by bureaucrats at all levels of government.

Since government politicians are mostly illiterate or inexperienced, they are heavily dependent on bureaucrats for all clerical work. While the unskilled bureaucrats are not able to complete their tasks effectively, on average almost 10 bureaucrats are paid for work that can be done by a single person. Thus, salaries being given to bureaucrats with public money is a form of corruption to loot the government exchequer. It is estimated that a whopping 10% of India's GDP is wasted on salaries of government employees while they do not deserve even a fraction of this money.

BUREAUCRATIC AND POLITICAL CORRUPTION

Today, no government in India is willing to stop corruption because now it has become the lifeblood of Indian bureaucrats and politicians. All major global anti-corruption organizations observe that corruption has been increasing at an alarming pace in India while the government has no plans and procedures to stop corruption in the country.

Now it appears that corruption has become an integral part of independent India while all State governments as well as the Central government have been encouraging corruption instead of removing it. While political corruption is rampant, bureaucratic naivety or inefficiency is the worst form of corruption. The survival of politicians and political parties depends on corruption money which is used to purchase voters, legislators, and commit all sorts of electoral frauds.

Almost all the politicians in the State governments are highly corrupt. But this report mainly covers the case studies of national political parties: Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP) of prime minister Narendra Modi and Congress owned and operated by Sonia Gandhi and

her son Rahul Gandhi. Although the Aam Aadmi Party (AAP) of Arvind Kejriwal is a local political group, it is embroiled in major corruption scandals and it appears that AAP is the only party in which almost all the politicians are corrupt. So, the report also covers AAP.

Bureaucrats work hand in glove with corrupt politicians to circumvent the law and indulge in corrupt practices. There is no administrative mechanism for the general public to get rid of corruption. Courts are also not quite willing to handle corruption cases because the Indian judiciary is largely controlled by corrupt politicians. Estimates suggest that India is losing around \$1 trillion annually to corruption. This amount is nearly 30% of India's GDP.

Now it is not only the bureaucratic and political corruption that is troubling ordinary Indians, but in recent years small groups of white-collar criminals have started operating like sophisticated extortion gangs in different cities of India. They bribe the corrupt bureaucrats to circumvent the law and extort money from ordinary citizens.

Effects of Corruption in India. Photo: RMN News Service

Police and law-enforcement agencies are not trained to deal with white-collar crimes such as corruption by organized criminal groups which operate openly in different localities. As bureaucrats also lack knowledge to operate in the modern information-driven world, they are not capable of addressing public complaints on corruption. Strangely, most bureaucrats do not treat corruption as a crime. Since the administrative systems have totally collapsed in India, corruption is increasing at a rapid

pace. Government officials and politicians keep sending people's complaints from one office to another like a post office, but they never take administrative decisions to catch and punish the corrupt officials.

Finally, the aggrieved citizens are left with no other option but to approach the courts. But since courts are always overcrowded and judicial systems are inefficient, the court decisions are either inordinately delayed or lack justice. The less said about the Indian courts, the better.

Now corruption has reduced India to a level of criminalized kleptocracy, in which all the four pillars of democracy have collapsed. As a result, India continues to be a poor, underdeveloped country. The sorry plight of Indians indicates that India has already become a politically unstable banana republic with rampant lawlessness, corruption, and exploitation of the ordinary citizens. Now India should formally appear in the list of banana republics such as Botswana, Guatemala, Nigeria, Zambia, and Cuba.

If the situation is not controlled immediately, it is expected that international sanctions will be imposed on India because of the government's failure to stop increasing crime and corruption in the country.

OVERVIEW OF CORRUPTION IN INDIA

In his Gettysburg speech of 1863, the-then U.S. President Abraham Lincoln introduced America's representative democracy as the "government of the people, by the people, for the people." Inspired by this principle of democracy, many progressive nations adopted it as the system of governance for the well-being of their people. India was one of them. However, things have gone topsy-turvy during the past 75 years - after India got independence from the Britishers in 1947.

Today, India has completely distorted Lincoln's slogan and it has become a "country of the corrupt, by the corrupt, for the corrupt." While corruption has spread like a pandemic disease in the entire country, there is no government plan that describes and deals with corruption. Rather, the existing anti-corruption laws are misused and misinterpreted to protect corrupt bureaucrats, politicians, and top corporate executives. The convictions happen only in those cases in which the politicians in the ruling political party have to settle a score with their opponents. Since courts are complicit in corruption crimes, they do not use anti-corruption laws to punish corrupt bureaucrats and politicians.

Estimates [suggest](#) that India is losing around \$1 trillion annually to corruption. This amount is nearly 30% of India's GDP. Moreover, the [money](#) stashed by Indians in Swiss banks - where usually corruption / black money is kept - rose by over 50% to Rs. 7,000 crore in 2017. While recent data is not available, it is believed that the amount of black money amassed by Indians has increased considerably during the past five years. [1 US\$ ~ Indian Rs. 80]

As corruption has been increasing exponentially during the past few years, the Supreme Court of India asked the government to set up the office of Lokpal, the top anti-corruption ombudsman in India. Although the Lokpal was established in March 2019, let alone resolving corruption cases, it could not formalize its processes in five years of its formation. Corruption is still increasing rapidly in different forms.

While political and bureaucratic corruption has become a pain in the neck for commoners in India, there is no effective agency which can give relief from corruption to the suffering citizens. The Lokayukta (anti-corruption ombudsman organization in the Indian States), vigilance departments of State governments, and India's top anti-corruption organization Central Vigilance Commission (CVC) are all toothless outfits that tend to protect the corrupt officials and encourage corruption. They simply turn a blind eye to the corruption cases in which government politicians and working bureaucrats are involved.

The procedures of anti-corruption agencies to accept public complaints on corruption are so slow and cumbersome that ordinary citizens feel scared to file their complaints against corrupt officials. The public grievance monitoring systems of the State as well as Central governments are also totally ineffective. After receiving complaints from the citizens, these systems send them to some random departments in a mechanical way and abruptly close the cases without giving relief to the complainants.

Government officials keep throwing public complaints from one desk to another without taking conclusive decisions on the complaints. Finally, the aggrieved citizens are left with no other option but to approach the courts. But if courts have to do everything, why do we need politicians and government officials? The administrative systems have totally collapsed in India.

While corruption is happening openly, most corruption cases involving top bureaucrats and ruling politicians do not get reported. As most Indian journalists are corrupt, Indian media is under the tight control of the government. When some corruption cases appear in the non-traditional media (such as news sites), the government ignores them and

makes false claims that no corruption is happening under the government. The truth, however, is that corruption - which has been persisting for decades under all governments - is happening and increasing at every step in the country.

Although a slew of anti-corruption laws exist in India, the rising corruption in the country indicates that these laws are not effective. The anti-corruption laws that are supposed to check corruption include Indian Penal Code, 1860; Prevention of Corruption Act, 1988; Benami Transactions (Prohibition) Act, 1988 to prohibit benami transactions; Prevention of Money Laundering Act, 2002; among others.

Moreover, the Lokpal and Lokayuktas Act, 2013 which came into force from January 2014, seeks to provide for the establishment of the institution of Lokpal to inquire into allegations of corruption against certain public functionaries in India. Whistle Blowers Protection Act, 2011, which [provides](#) a mechanism to investigate alleged corruption and misuse of power by public servants and also protect anyone who exposes alleged wrongdoing in government bodies, projects, and offices, received the assent of the President of India on May 9, 2014, and was pending for notification by the Central Government. The implementation of the Act got delayed because amendments pertaining to safeguards against certain disclosures relevant to national security could not be incorporated.

India is also a signatory to the United Nations Convention against Corruption (UNCAC) since 2005 (ratified 2011). The Convention covers a wide range of acts of corruption and also proposes certain preventive policies. While corruption can take place in many forms, punishment for bribery - which is the basic form of corruption in India - can range from six months to seven years of imprisonment.

At present, thousands of complaints alleging various misconducts are under inquiry relating to public servants under the jurisdiction of the CVC. As the decisions on corruption cases get inordinately delayed, CVC says investigation into complaints is an ongoing process and the Commission regularly monitors the pendency with the Chief Vigilance Officers (CVOs) to ensure time-bound completion of the same.

Among the corruption complaints received by the Central Vigilance Commission (CVC) in 2023, railway employees had the highest number of complaints filed against them, followed by employees of Delhi's local bodies and public sector banks. Reports of September 2024 [reveal](#) that CVC received 74,203 corruption complaints against

government functionaries. Out of these, 66,373 complaints were addressed and 7,830 are pending.

However, these are misleading [figures](#) because like other departments CVC counts a complaint disposed of after sending it mechanically to some random department. For example, the CVC informed me with the following email dated September 30, 2024 that my complaint has been forwarded to Chief Vigilance Officer (CVO) in Delhi Government and Registrar Cooperative Societies (RCS) office of Delhi Government.

Unfortunately, however, the CVOs in State governments ignore the CVC directives. And in this case, the RCS office of Delhi Government - which is one of the most corrupt departments of India - never takes action against corrupt officials. Therefore, all this exercise to check corruption has gone futile.

Example of a CVC email forwarded to Delhi Government to investigate a corruption case

As the CVC works with opaque systems, it is not possible to know the names and titles of convicted officials. The delays in investigations, according to CVC, are on account of a multitude of reasons such as lack of adequate officers in certain offices, complexity of investigations, time taken to follow the laid down procedure, non-cooperation of the suspect officers, etc.

As the government does not encourage the citizens to file their complaints, India's leading anti-corruption agencies have made the corruption complaints filing and

investigation processes very complex. Also, the top investigation agency the Central Bureau of Investigation ([CBI](#)) is terribly slow in investigating normal corruption cases while CBI works very fast when the ruling political party directs it to investigate the cases of its political opponents.

ICRR 2024: Key Facts

- Corruption in India is increasing exponentially.
- Corruption cases of the ruling regime never get investigated.
- Bureaucrats enjoy full impunity in their acts of corruption.
- Judicial corruption is increasing rapidly.
- Courts are mostly complicit in corruption crimes.
- Oligarchs close to the government politicians commit financial crimes blatantly.
- Investigation agencies are negligent and unskilled to handle corruption cases.
- Anti-corruption laws are not followed.
- Courts easily grant bail to corrupt politicians and even when trial is running, politicians claim that they have been acquitted by the courts.
- A couple of old lawyers who belong(ed) to the Congress party have been trying to protect politicians involved in serious cases of crime and corruption. Court judges succumb to these lawyers' pressure.
- If politicians are jailed for a few days, they enjoy luxurious treatment in jails.
- Corruption is equally rampant in the Central and State governments.
- With opaque corporate funding through electoral bonds, political corruption by the ruling regime has increased manifold.
- In return to illicit corporate funds, the government does not take back loans given to corporates. Banks have written off [bad loans](#) worth Rs. 10.57 lakh crore in the last five financial years. This is the most dreaded form of organized corruption.
- As the leaders of opposition political parties are equally corrupt, they do not oppose government corruption.
- Corrupt politicians get off scot-free by claiming that the corruption cases against them are politically motivated.
- Since politicians, bureaucrats, police, and judges have formed a criminal gang in India, there is no forum for citizens where they could complain and get rid of corruption.

ABOUT INDIA CORRUPTION RESEARCH REPORT

The India Corruption Research Report 2024 (ICRR 2024) carries information on the extent of corruption in India, corruption-prevention laws, complicity of government organs in major corruption cases, findings of a perception survey, case studies of major scandals, flawed investigation processes, weak government-to-citizen (G2C) interfaces, limitations of the anti-corruption authorities, and so on.

The information in the report is included from the primary as well as secondary sources and my personal experiences as a journalist and anti-corruption activist. In the past few years, I have filed more than 100 complaints with the government's anti-corruption agencies against the corrupt government functionaries including Indian Administrative Service (IAS) and Indian Police Service (IPS) officers.

Some of the actual letters from different government departments in corruption cases are linked in this report. Unfortunately, however, no formal investigation took place in all these cases and the government functionaries continue to commit acts of corruption with full impunity provided by the corrupt political and administrative systems. Such perfunctory letters are written by the government departments to deceive the complainants by creating a false impression that action is being taken on the complaints.

CORRUPTION PERCEPTION SURVEY

As part of this research project, an original perception survey was launched on RMN News Service to collect primary views of the citizens. The following 10 questions were presented to the respondents to take their votes.

Is India a corrupt country?

Yes

No

Are you affected by corruption in India?

Yes

No

Who is mainly responsible for corruption in India?

Bureaucrats

Politicians

Private Companies

What is the impact of corruption in India?

Death of Democracy

Human Rights Violations

Inflation

Injustice

Poverty

Hunger

Unemployment

Are Indian anti-corruption agencies working honestly?

Yes

No

Are corrupt Indian bureaucrats and politicians punished suitably?

Yes

No

Is there a criminal nexus between business oligarchs and top politicians in India?

Yes

No

Are Indian courts handling corruption cases effectively?

Yes

No

Should Indian corruption crimes be prosecuted in international courts?

Yes

No

Is imprisonment a sufficient punishment for corruption crimes?

Yes

No

The findings of the perception [survey](#) are given below. These findings were recorded up to September 2024 and presented in the following charts.

- A whopping 88% of people believe that India is a corrupt country.
- Corruption has adversely affected 79% of the people in India. It can be inferred that the other 21% who are not affected are committing corruption crimes.

- As India's bureaucrats blatantly defy laws and commit financial crimes with impunity, 48% people say in the survey that bureaucrats are responsible for corruption while 43% believe that politicians are committing corruption crimes. A smaller number of people – 9% – say that private companies which bribe the government functionaries are responsible for corruption.
- Twenty-four percent people believe that corruption has destroyed the democratic systems in India and 23% say corruption is causing unemployment in the country. Injustice, human rights violations, inflation, poverty, and hunger are the other adverse effects of corruption.
- Almost all the respondents (86%) say that the anti-corruption agencies of India are not working honestly. All the anti-corruption agencies – such as the Lokpal, Central Vigilance Commission (CVC), Lokayuktas, Central Bureau of Investigation (CBI), Economic Offences Wings (EOWs) of Police, State police departments, and others – are working hand in glove with the corrupt government functionaries.
- Since corrupt bureaucrats and politicians enjoy full impunity and the judicial systems are quite dysfunctional in India, 87% people said in the survey that the corrupt officials and political leaders are not being punished suitably. As a result, corruption is increasing rapidly in India.
- When asked if there is a criminal nexus between business oligarchs and top politicians in India, almost all - 79% - respondents said that there is a criminal nexus between business oligarchs and top politicians.
- Similarly, 71% people believe that Indian courts are not handling corruption cases effectively, as most court judges are either ignorant or involved in corruption crimes.
- As many as 75% respondents said in the survey that Indian corruption crimes should be prosecuted in international courts because the Indian courts are complicit in crimes and tend to grant bail to the jailed criminals who are accused of serious financial crimes.
- Moreover, 61% people said that imprisonment is not a sufficient punishment for corruption crimes because the affluent criminals - including politicians, bureaucrats, and businessmen - are secretly provided luxurious facilities in Indian jails and courts often release them without any punishment.

These findings are depicted in the charts given below.

Is India a corrupt country?

A whopping 88% of people believe that India is a corrupt country.

Are you affected by corruption in India?

Corruption has adversely affected 79% of the people in India. It can be inferred that the other 21% who are not affected are committing corruption crimes.

Who is mainly responsible for corruption in India?

As India's bureaucrats blatantly defy laws and commit financial crimes with impunity, 48% people say in the survey that bureaucrats are responsible for corruption while 43% believe that politicians are committing corruption crimes. A smaller number of people – 9% – say that private companies which bribe the government functionaries are responsible for corruption.

What is the impact of corruption in India?

Twenty-four percent people believe that corruption has destroyed the democratic systems in India and 23% say corruption is causing unemployment in the country. Injustice, human rights violations, inflation, poverty, and hunger are the other adverse effects of corruption.

Almost all the respondents (86%) say that the anti-corruption agencies of India are not working honestly. All the anti-corruption agencies – such as the Lokpal, Central Vigilance Commission (CVC), Lokayuktas, Central Bureau of Investigation (CBI), Economic Offences Wings (EOWs) of Police, State police departments, and others – are working hand in glove with the corrupt government functionaries.

Since corrupt bureaucrats and politicians enjoy full impunity and the judicial systems are quite dysfunctional in India, 87% people said in the survey that the corrupt officials and political leaders are not being punished suitably. As a result, corruption is increasing rapidly in India.

Is there a criminal nexus between business oligarchs and top politicians in India?

When asked if there is a criminal nexus between business oligarchs and top politicians in India, almost all - 79% - respondents said that there is a criminal nexus between business oligarchs and top politicians.

Are Indian courts handling corruption cases effectively?

Similarly, 71% people believe that Indian courts are not handling corruption cases effectively, as most court judges are either ignorant or involved in corruption crimes.

Should Indian corruption crimes be prosecuted in international courts?

As many as 75% respondents said in the survey that Indian corruption crimes should be prosecuted in international courts because the Indian courts are complicit in crimes and tend to grant bail to the jailed criminals who are accused of serious financial crimes.

Is imprisonment a sufficient punishment for corruption crimes?

Moreover, 61% people said that imprisonment is not a sufficient punishment for corruption crimes because the affluent criminals - including politicians, bureaucrats, and businessmen - are secretly provided luxurious facilities in Indian jails and courts often release them without any punishment.

GLOBAL OBSERVATIONS ON CORRUPTION IN INDIA

While India continues to be one of the most corrupt countries in the world, the few convictions that are taking place in corruption cases are driven by political reasons rather than an attempt to weed out general corruption from the country. The corruption cases in which the top government politicians are involved never get investigated. In general, the bureaucratic and political corruption is so rampant in India that the culprits hardly get caught or jailed and enjoy full government impunity to continue their corrupt acts.

The U.S. Department of State in its annual [country report](#) released on April 22, 2024 has revealed extreme corruption and human rights violations in India. In an exclusive Section 4: “*Corruption in Government*,” the report asserts that corruption was present at multiple levels of Indian government. The U.S. report adds that NGOs reported the payment of bribes to expedite services, such as police protection, school admission, water supply, and government assistance. According to the report, civil society organizations drew public attention to corruption throughout the year, including through demonstrations and websites that featured stories of corruption.

While rampant corruption is happening everywhere in India, the untamed bureaucrats are blatantly defying laws that are supposed to prevent corruption. The 2023 Corruption Perceptions Index ([CPI](#)) released on January 30, 2024 by Transparency International reveals extreme corruption in India.

According to CPI, India shows score fluctuations small enough that no firm conclusions can be drawn on any significant change, but the country’s score dropped to 39 in 2023 from 40 a year ago. That means corruption has increased in the country of 1.4 billion people. According to a *Times of India* [report](#) of January 30, 2024, India’s CPI rank slipped from 85 in 2022 to 93 in 2023, which indicates more corruption.

The latest 2023 Rule of Law Index of the World Justice Project (WJP) [reveals](#) increasing judicial corruption in India. According to WJP analysis, the Indian judicial systems are plagued by corruption while judges enjoy full impunity without any punishment for their acts of corruption. The Corruption Perceptions Index ([CPI](#)) released in January 2024 by Transparency International states that the world is experiencing a decline in the functioning of justice systems. According to Transparency International, countries with

the lowest scores in the Rule of Law Index are also scoring very low on the CPI, highlighting a clear connection between access to justice and corruption.

The details of judicial corruption are given in the “*India Judicial Research Report 2024: Decline of the Indian Judiciary*”. [You can [click here](#) to download and read the research report.]

As a result of bureaucratic and political corruption, the [people](#) of India are suffering under unprecedented inflation, pollution, hunger, unemployment, human rights violations, injustice, lawlessness, and extreme misery.

COMPLICIT ANTI-CORRUPTION AGENCIES OF INDIA

The anti-corruption agencies in India are either scared of the government politicians or complicit in crimes being committed by bureaucrats and politicians. That is why they simply ignore the corruption complaints against government functionaries. Moreover, the investigating officers are so unskilled and almost illiterate that they cannot understand the complaints. As a result, there are inordinate delays in resolving the corruption cases or the culprits never get punished.

Now it appears that all the anti-corruption agencies of India - such as the Lokpal, Central Vigilance Commission (CVC), Lokayuktas, Central Bureau of Investigation (CBI), Economic Offences Wings (EOWs) of Police, State police departments, and also the Department of Personnel and Training (DoPT) as well as the Cabinet Secretariat - are working hand in glove with the corrupt government functionaries.

They take action in corruption cases against bureaucrats or politicians of opposition parties only when directed by the top political rulers. When the members of the public complain against corrupt officials, they simply ignore the complaints or send perfunctory letters here and there to discard the complaints from citizens. The bureaucrats - who work as uncivil masters rather than civil servants - never resolve public grievances and treat citizens as slaves.

As a journalist and anti-corruption activist, I have filed several complaints against the corrupt officials over the years. I have observed that the anti-corruption investigation and the prosecution agencies are complicit in corruption crimes as they have formed a

criminal gang with the corrupt officials. While courts are not fully equipped to handle corruption cases, the anti-corruption agencies have failed to punish corrupt officials.

Therefore, I do not get fair treatment on my complaints which are discarded under one pretext or another mainly because the Indian government is not willing to stop corruption. So, the corrupt officials never get caught and punished. They keep committing more corruption crimes in connivance with the anti-corruption agencies.

As a result of the impunity provided to the crooks by the top anti-corruption officers, corruption is increasing exponentially in all parts of the country. Consequently, the people of India are facing a severe socio-economic crisis and India is getting a bad name at all global forums.

DELIBERATE NEGLIGENCE IN APPLYING ANTI-CORRUPTION LAWS

While most government officials and corruption investigating officers lack English communication skills, they do not understand the complaints to take proper action on them. At the same time, they are extremely careless and ignorant of the prevailing anti-corruption laws that they must apply to begin prosecution in different cases.

If the anti-corruption authorities simply apply the following laws, hundreds or thousands of Indian bureaucrats and politicians will be convicted and jailed. In fact, their number would be so large that the government will have to build new jails and detention centers for them.

Some of these laws to deal with emerging financial crimes including corruption are the Prevention of Corruption Act, 1988 ([PC ACT](#)), Chapter IX of the Indian Penal Code ([IPC](#)), 1860 or the new Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita or BNS Sections, Vigilance Manual of the CVC, prevention of grand corruption and rent-seeking regulations.

THE PREVENTION OF CORRUPTION (AMENDMENT) ACT, 2018 states that:

For sections 7, 8, 9 and 10 of the principal Act, the following sections shall be substituted, namely:—

“7. Any public servant who,—

(a) obtains or accepts or attempts to obtain from any person, an undue advantage, with the intention to perform or cause performance of public duty

improperly or dishonestly or to forbear or cause forbearance to perform such duty either by himself or by another public servant; or

(b) obtains or accepts or attempts to obtain, an undue advantage from any person as a reward for the improper or dishonest performance of a public duty or for forbearing to perform such duty either by himself or another public servant; or

(c) performs or induces another public servant to perform improperly or dishonestly a public duty or to forbear performance of such duty in anticipation of or in consequence of accepting an undue advantage from any person...

shall be punishable with imprisonment for a term which shall not be less than three years but which may extend to seven years and shall also be liable to fine.

The Vigilance Manual 2021 of Central Vigilance Commission (CVC) of India [states](#) that:

Corruption is manifested in various forms such as bribery, nepotism, willful action or willful inaction to benefit someone or to deny benefit to someone known or unknown. It also states that corruption includes cases of favoritism and failure to follow laid down processes leading to unintended benefit to someone or denial of benefit to the deserving.

Also, a case of [rent-seeking](#) takes place when the public functionaries distort the government rules and misuse their authority surreptitiously for personal gains.

The concept of rent-seeking applies to corruption by public servants and elected leaders who solicit and extract "bribe" or "rent" for using their legal but discretionary authority for awarding legitimate or illegitimate benefits to clients or individuals or organizations.

Rent-seeking is directly related to government corruption. In such cases of organized white-collar crimes, the actual transaction of bribe money is not visible. Therefore, an investigation must be initiated after the collection of circumstantial evidence to track the flow of money.

Grand corruption [happens](#) when top government functionaries or politicians subvert the political, legal, and economic systems for personal gains or for taking undue advantages. Grand corruption - described as the abuse of public power for private gain by a nation's leaders (kleptocrats) – has devastating consequences for the citizens of a country. Grand

corruption deprives people of their fundamental rights and disturbs the peace and security in a country.

Actually, grand corruption cannot happen without the collusion of courts. And in the anti-corruption laws, the transaction of bribe is not required to be tracked. Rather, it is assumed that corruption crime has happened if a government functionary such as a court judge misuses their authority to give a wrong or biased judgment.

But the anti-corruption mechanisms of courts neither apply anti-corruption laws to prosecute and convict judges nor do they use these laws in top bureaucratic or political corruption cases. In order to weed out corruption from India, there is an immediate need to apply these anti-corruption laws and revamp the corruption investigation and prosecution processes. Since the corruption complaint systems such as the Centralized Public Grievance Redress and Monitoring System (CPGRAMS) of the government are defective, the government should design and deploy an effective online mechanism to receive and monitor corruption complaints from the citizens.

While it is extremely difficult to revive the defunct systems in the States, a proper replacement of the CPGRAMS can check corruption to a greater extent. However, as the government bureaucrats and politicians are highly corrupt, they do not take any action to revamp the CPGRAMS mechanism.

SUGGESTED ACTION TO REVAMP CORRUPTION PREVENTION PROCESSES

Since the existing processes to prevent corruption in India are not working, the government should redesign and revamp these processes. Some of the steps for this exercise are given below.

- 1.** Develop, design, and deploy a new complaints management system to replace the defunct CPGRAMS.
- 2.** Use flowcharts, videos, and other multimedia instructional content to describe the complete, end-to-end process of dealing with a corruption complaint from a citizen.
- 3.** The government functionaries who receive the complaints should understand them, write their comments and instructions for the investigating officers and then forward the

complaints to concerned departments for investigation. They should not work as mere postal workers to deliver letters blindly to the investigating departments.

4. Issue formal notices to the officials against whom the complaints are filed and direct them to respond within 15 days. The coordinating officers should study the response from the accused officers and if the response is not satisfactory, they should take action against the respondents. If required, the accused officials must be suspended before beginning the investigation or prosecution against them.

5. Put all these details transparently on the online complaints management system so that the complainant and the accused are aware of the progress of the case.

6. Investigate and prosecute all the cases in a fast-track process so that the corrupt officials could be immediately convicted and jailed.

7. Allow the complainants to participate in the investigation hearings with the accused so that they could argue the case, leading to their prosecution and conviction.

8. Do not close the cases arbitrarily and keep the complainants informed at every step of the investigation and prosecution so that they could provide their inputs for a fair investigation.

9. Employ domain experts with perfect process management and communication skills to support the existing government officials who are not quite qualified to understand and use the contemporary methods to deal with corruption.

10. Enhance the use of digital platforms to receive corruption complaints, hold live-streamed investigation hearings, and update the cases on a revamped digital user interface.

These are the indicative steps that the government should take to prevent and stop corruption in India. After using them at DoPT, Ministry of Home Affairs (MHA), and the Cabinet Secretariat, they will also form the basis for improving the corruption-prevention laws and procedures in different anti-corruption agencies such as the Lokpal, CVC, Lokayuktas, CBI, EOWs of Police, and so on.

Along with these steps, it should be the fundamental / human right of the people to live in a corruption-free environment. With simplified processes, the courts should accept corruption complaints as the cases of human rights violations.

Widehouse Corruption Scandal of Delhi

It is a citywide crime and corruption racket which began about 6 years ago in Delhi. The intensity of this crime increased in 2024 and it is continuing.

The citywide construction-cum-corruption racket – termed as Widehouse Corruption Scandal – is being run by local criminals who operate as management committee (MC) members of Delhi's cooperative group housing societies (CGHS) in connivance with crooked politicians, corrupt bureaucrats, complicit police officials, dishonest members of judiciary, and builders' mafia.

After the criminal enterprise of Nazi Germany during the Holocaust for the genocide of millions of European Jews, the Widehouse corruption [scandal](#) is the largest organized massacre not only in India but also in the world. In this criminal attack, millions of people are victims of a single crime which is being brazenly supported by the Indian government to harm its own citizens.

The estimated annual corruption money involved in this scandal is hundreds (or may be thousands) of crores of rupees (equivalent to millions of dollars) and nearly 2 million (20 lakh) residents are the direct victims in this criminal case. If not stopped, the harmful construction will continue in Delhi for many years – even until 2030.

You can [click here](#) to read the full report on the Widehouse Corruption Scandal. It includes facts, figures, names of accused officials, government documents, infographics, photographs, video links, and the actions expected from the Indian and international law-enforcement agencies. The details of this crime including dozens of documents are [available](#) at the Public Grievance Monitoring System (PGMS) of Delhi Government under PGMS Grievance No. 2021120462 dated 14.10.2021. But the corrupt officials are not taking any action to stop this crime.

Photo: Affected by the Widehouse scandal, senior citizens in a group housing society of Dwarka in New Delhi urge the government to save them from dust pollution, noise pollution, and air pollution of extended floor area ratio (FAR) construction activity.

Photo and Campaign by Rakesh Raman / RMN Foundation

FORMS OF CORRUPTION AND ITS IMPACT

Corruption is not only a crime but it is also an immoral act. Among the other descriptions of corruption, the global anti-corruption organization Transparency International suggests that corruption thrives on a low level of transparency. The factors which encourage systemic corruption include weak judiciary, discretionary powers of government officials, centralized power structures, lack of transparency, and impunity.

Traditional Forms of Corruption		
Bribery	Extortion	Embezzlement
Factors That Encourage Corruption		
Conflicting Incentives	Discretionary Powers	Monopolistic Structures
Lack of Transparency	Low Pay	Culture of Impunity

It is observed that corruption has multiple adverse effects on the citizens, the entire society, and the economy of a country. The effects of corruption include poor quality of public services, unemployment, lack of justice, increased inequality among people, and so on. All these effects can lead to social unrest in a country.

CORRUPTION FACTORS IN INDIA

The factors that contribute to increased corruption in India include flawed electoral processes, political and bureaucratic illiteracy, lack of domain expertise among government officials, inefficient and obsolete administrative systems, lack of transparency, and weak policy implementation mechanisms.

The factors also include lack of opportunities for the public to participate in the administrative reform process, archaic school and college education systems, centralized administration, limited technology usage, low or no press freedom, poverty, and government's attacks on civil society organizations.

Obviously, it is almost impossible for any government in India to overcome all these challenges while the corrupt and corruption are thriving. Although Indian politicians

loudly claim that they will weed out corruption from the country, corruption has always been increasing rapidly.

Main Factors That Contribute to Increasing Corruption in India		
Flawed Electoral Processes	Political and Bureaucratic Illiteracy	Lack of Domain Expertise
Obsolete Administrative Systems	Lack of Transparency	Weak Policy Implementation
Archaic Education Systems	Centralized Administration	Limited Technology Usage
Low or No Press Freedom	Attacks on Civil Society Organizations	Poverty

Corruption was the main factor for the debacle of the Congress-led government in the 2014 and again in 2019 Lok Sabha elections. Congress tried to use corruption in the government as the main rhetoric to defeat the ruling Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP) in the 2024 Lok Sabha election, but its strategy boomeranged and BJP won again.

CASE STUDIES OF GRAND CORRUPTION

GRAND CORRUPTION CASES IN INDIAN POLITICS

It is not possible to survive and thrive in Indian politics if you are not corrupt. You can leapfrog in the dirty political arena if you are a history-sheeter with a solid criminal record which must include embezzlement, dacoity, vandalism, murders, rapes, and robbery.

Today, the majority of the successful Indian politicians have such a distinguished criminal record. While ordinary citizens are suffering under their atrocities, the Indian bureaucrats, court judges, police, and security forces behave as the slaves of the criminal politicians and never try to protect citizens and their rights. The corruption cases in which top politicians are involved never get investigated properly and discarded to protect the politicians. A few of these cases are described below.

MODANI CORRUPTION SCANDAL

Hindenburg Research - which is a U.S. investment research firm - has accused the Securities and Exchange Board of India (SEBI) chairperson Madhabi Puri Buch and her husband Dhaval Buch of complicity in one of the most heinous corporate fraud scandals.

In a [report](#) published on August 10, 2024, Hindenburg Research claimed that the SEBI chief had a stake in obscure offshore entities used in the Adani money siphoning scandal.

Earlier, in its investigative [report](#) released on January 24, 2023, Hindenburg Research said that the Adani Group and its chairman Gautam Adani have engaged in a brazen stock manipulation and accounting fraud scheme over the course of decades. The report accused Adani of committing one of the biggest corporate frauds in the world. In its latest [report](#), Hindenburg has quoted whistleblower documents to reveal that SEBI - which was supposed to investigate the Adani scam case - has shown little interest to explore Adani's alleged undisclosed web of offshore shell entities in Mauritius or other places.

Hindenburg states that its January 2023 report exposed a web of offshore - primarily Mauritius-based - shell entities used for suspected billions of dollars of undisclosed related party transactions, undisclosed investment and stock manipulation by the Adani Group. It also said that the Adani Group was operating "the largest con in corporate history".

Since then, according to Hindenburg, despite the evidence, along with over 40 independent [media investigations](#) corroborating and expanding on its original work, Indian securities regulator SEBI has taken no public action against the Adani Group.

Hindenburg suspects that SEBI is likely to impose mere token, technical violations on the Adani Group despite the breadth and magnitude of the issues.

Instead of investigating the enormity of fraud in the Adani case, the SEBI preferred to intimidate Hindenburg with legal action. On June 27, 2024, SEBI sent Hindenburg a vague 'show cause' notice, which according to Hindenburg, did not allege any factual error in its report.

In its July 2024 [response](#) to the 'show cause' notice, Hindenburg found it odd how SEBI – a regulator specifically set up to prevent fraudulent practices – showed little interest in meaningfully pursuing the parties that ran a secret offshore shell empire engaging in

billions of dollars of undisclosed related party transactions through public companies while propping up its stocks through a network of sham investment entities.

In its original Adani report, Hindenburg cites documents from the Directorate of Revenue Intelligence (DRI) which alleged that Adani “grossly” overvalued the import valuation of key power equipment, using offshore shell entities to siphon and launder money from the Indian public.

Hindenburg adds that a subsequent investigation by non-profit project Adani Watch in December 2023 showed how a web of offshore entities, controlled by Gautam Adani’s brother, Vinod Adani, were recipients of funds from the alleged over-invoicing of power equipment.

In one complex structure, according to Hindenburg, a Vinod Adani controlled company had invested in “Global Dynamic Opportunities Fund” (“GDOF”) in Bermuda, a British overseas territory and tax haven, which then invested in IPE Plus Fund 1, a fund registered in Mauritius, another tax haven.

Whistleblower documents obtained by Hindenburg show that Madhabi Buch, the current chairperson of SEBI, and her husband had stakes in both obscure offshore funds used in the Adani scandal. “We had previously noted Adani’s total confidence in continuing to operate without the risk of serious regulatory intervention, suggesting that this may be explained through Adani’s relationship with SEBI chairperson, Madhabi Buch,” Hindenburg said in its latest report.

“What we hadn’t realized: the current SEBI chairperson and her husband, Dhaval Buch, had hidden stakes in the exact same obscure offshore Bermuda and Mauritius funds, found in the same complex nested structure, used by Vinod Adani,” Hindenburg adds. According to Hindenburg, Madhabi Buch and her husband Dhaval Buch first appear to have opened their account with IPE Plus Fund 1 on June 5, 2015 in Singapore, per whistleblower documents.

A declaration of funds, signed by a principal at IIFL states that the source of the investment is “salary” and the couple's net worth is estimated at \$10 million, Hindenburg states.

In a vaguely written [statement](#) issued on August 11, 2024, SEBI chairperson Madhabi Puri Buch and her husband Dhaval Buch called it an attempted "character assassination" by

Hindenburg in response to SEBI action. However, this statement does not refute any of the accusations made by Hindenburg in its reports.

With a standard statement, the Adani Group on August 11 also [rejected](#) the latest report by Hindenburg Research as "recycled claims".

Supreme Court Role in Adani Money Laundering Case

As the Supreme Court of India has become a toothless outfit, it has failed once again to deliver justice in the money laundering and accounting fraud case of the Adani Group.

In its judgment of January 3, 2024, a Supreme Court bench headed by Chief Justice of India D. Y. Chandrachud said there were no grounds to transfer the probe to a special investigation team (SIT).

The court relied on the opaque and sketchy investigation conducted by the Securities and Exchange Board of India (SEBI) which – like the Supreme Court – is a complicit organization trying to exonerate the Adani Group and its chairman Gautam Adani.

It was [reported](#) in January 2024 that SEBI had investigated 22 of the 24 cases in the Adani case and the Supreme Court had given it three more months to complete the investigation. But so far the SEBI probe findings have not been made public.

In his [tweet](#) on January 3, 2024, Gautam Adani celebrated the Supreme Court decision with his remarks, “Truth has prevailed. Satyameva Jayate” with the apparent indication that he has been exonerated in the case. But oligarch Gautam Adani did not mention that the Supreme Court and other law-enforcement agencies are protecting him unscrupulously because he is a partner of India’s prime minister (PM) [Narendra Modi](#) who himself is allegedly involved in a number of corruption cases.

These cases include the PM-CARES Fund [case](#), Rafale corruption [case](#), Sri Lanka energy project [case](#) involving Adani Group, Modi-Adani [collusion](#) case, Sahara-Birla payoff [case](#), and a number of other [cases](#) in which Modi’s party colleagues are allegedly involved.

In fact, the Modi-Adani collusion case is termed as the Modani (portmanteau for Modi and Adani) corruption scandal, which is perhaps the biggest grand corruption crime in the history of mankind.

In this case, it is alleged that Gautam Adani colluded with Modi for about two decades to plunder India’s public assets. Since the Indian courts, law-enforcement agencies, and

media houses cannot dare to investigate or report about the Modi-Adani collusion case honestly, some [foreign publications](#) have been covering the stories of this corruption scandal involving billions of dollars.

Surprisingly, however, the Supreme Court ignored all the investigative reports of credible media organizations and acquitted Adani and his allegedly illicit businesses without holding a fair and transparent investigation.

In the past when Modi or his associates were accused in such cases, the Supreme Court took questionable decisions to favour Modi or formed perfunctory committees which could not dare to point the finger at Modi or his friends. It has happened in cases such as the Rafale [corruption case](#), Gujarat [massacre](#) case, [Article 370](#) case of Kashmir, Pegasus [spyware](#) case, draconian [demonetization](#) decision of Modi, cases of farmers' [protests](#), case of [PM-CARES Fund](#) of PM Modi, electronic voting machine ([EVM](#)) fraud case, the mysterious [death case](#) of Judge Loya (Brij Gopal Hari Kishan Loya), and many others.

Now it appears that the Supreme Court has become the Godi court (or lapdog court) of the Modi regime. The Supreme Court [judges](#) are either scared of the Modi regime or corrupt who want plum positions after their retirement. That is why they fail to deliver justice.

[You can [click here](#) to download and read “*India Judicial Research Report 2024: Decline of the Indian Judiciary*” to know the corruption and complicity of Indian courts.]

Also, in its [tweet](#) posted on September 12, 2024, Hindenburg said, “Swiss authorities have frozen more than \$310 million in funds across multiple Swiss bank accounts as part of a money laundering and securities forgery investigation into Adani, dating back as early as 2021.”

The tweet adds that prosecutors detailed how an Adani frontman invested in opaque BVI/Mauritius and Bermuda funds that almost exclusively owned Adani stocks. It has quoted a Swiss media outlet [report](#) of September 11 to reveal that a Swiss criminal court has taken action against the Adani Group.

While Adani is accused of a serious financial crime, the Supreme Court is trying to brush the case under the carpet with the formation of toothless committees or with the perfunctory probe by SEBI which cannot file any report that can get Adani prosecuted and convicted. In all probability, the findings of the SEBI report will not be made public and Adani will be acquitted of all the charges. Subsequently, Adani, Modi, and Modi's

colleagues will silence the opposition voices by saying that the Supreme Court has found that Adani is honest and no fraud has happened in this case.

If you evaluate the [judgments](#) of the Supreme Court through an Artificial Intelligence (AI)-based expert system, you will find that almost all the judgments, dismissal of petitions, or delays in decisions are either wrong or biased in favour of the Modi regime.

Weak Opposition

When the opposition leaders [questioned](#) Modi in the parliament on the Modi government's complicity in the Adani fraud, Modi did not even touch the Adani issue. Rather, he delivered a long rhetoric to praise himself and baselessly accuse the opposition party Congress of corruption. After some feeble protests, Congress did not pursue the Adani case.

In fact, it is a clear case of grand corruption and money laundering for which Adani or his associates should have been taken into custody for proper investigation. The Hindenburg report states that Adani's frauds included the formation of offshore shell entities to generate artificial turnover and money laundering.

But the SEBI and other law-enforcement agencies turned a blind eye to this alleged fraud and never tried to reveal the [information](#) publicly about these shell entities and the money laundered through them because Adani is a close friend of Modi.

The Financial Action Task Force (FATF), which sets global standards on beneficial ownership transparency, had [agreed](#) in March 2022 for tougher global beneficial ownership rules to stop criminals from hiding their illicit activities and dirty money behind secret corporate structures.

But the Indian agencies have deliberately ignored the FATF rules on [beneficial ownership](#) and did not publicly release the real beneficial ownership registers of Adani Group entities. It is possible that the dirty money is being used to [support](#) the terrorist financing activities that FATF is supposed to monitor.

Such reports are already coming. A March 2, 2023 media report [reveals](#) that an entity related to the Adani Group financially supported a company that violated sanctions imposed by the United Nations Security Council (UNSC) on trade with North Korea.

According to the report, the sanctioned company was owned by sons of Chang Chung-Ling, an Adani Group associate who appeared in the Hindenburg report for his

directorship of Adani entities. Actually, the [committee](#) formed by the Supreme Court, SEBI, and other law-enforcement agencies should have investigated all such allegations and live-streamed their interaction with the accused involved in this case.

The investigating agencies should also reveal if the corruption money made in the Rafale deal or the PM-CARES Fund has been invested in the Adani Group, as these cases have never been probed thoroughly.

Since the Supreme Court committee, SEBI, and the other law-enforcement agencies such as the Enforcement Directorate (ED) or the Central Bureau of Investigation (CBI) are not expected to act honestly, the Adani case should be prosecuted in international forums outside India.

The U.S., for example, can treat this case of [significant corruption](#) under Section 7031(c) of the annual Department of State, Foreign Operations, and Related Programs Appropriations Act or the Global Magnitsky sanctions program. Similarly, the UK can prosecute it under the UK Global Anti-Corruption Sanctions Regime.

Finally, the Modi-Adani case of grand corruption should be prosecuted in the International Anti-Corruption Court ([IACC](#)) proposed by Integrity Initiatives International and Club de Madrid, which is a group led by former democratic Presidents and Prime Ministers from around the world.

DELHI GOVERNMENT CORRUPTION AND LIQUOR SCANDAL

The Central Bureau of Investigation (CBI) - which is probing the massive Delhi liquor scam - has desired to hold similar investigations in Punjab because the dubious Delhi liquor (or excise) policy has been implemented in Punjab also.

Former Delhi chief minister (CM) and Aam Aadmi Party (AAP) leader Arvind Kejriwal was in jail for about five months for his alleged involvement in Delhi liquor mafia case. A number of other AAP politicians were also jailed in this case, but they have been released on bail by corrupt Indian courts while the case is underway.

During a [bail hearing](#) of Kejriwal on September 5, 2024, the CBI - through its advocate - claimed that the Delhi liquor scandal has a connection with Punjab where AAP is running the government. The CBI also alleged that Kejriwal's party is arm-twisting liquor businesses in Punjab to pay bribes if they have to stay in the liquor trade. The central

agency also maintains that Kejriwal and AAP used bribe money to contest the 2022 Goa Assembly election.

Since the AAP government led by CM Bhagwant Mann also used the Delhi liquor policy, CBI wants to investigate the Punjab case as well. However, the CBI [complained](#) in the Supreme Court that Kejriwal is influencing the Punjab Government to obstruct a CBI probe in the state.

In March 2024, a former Punjab Congress leader Ravneet Singh Bittu - who is now a minister in Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP) - had [asserted](#) that Bhagwant Mann will soon be arrested because he implemented the liquor policy that led to the imprisonment of several AAP leaders in Delhi.

In his video messages released on March 22, 2024 in [Hindi](#) and [Punjabi](#) languages, Bittu said that a few Punjab AAP politicians including Bhagwant Mann are involved in Punjab liquor scandal and they will be arrested.

In the ongoing liquor mafia case, Kejriwal's other colleagues – including Manish Sisodia and Sanjay Singh – were also jailed. In October last year, while rejecting the bail [application](#) of Sisodia, the Supreme Court said there is a possible embezzlement of Rs. 338 crore in the liquor scam case. But the embezzled money has not yet been recovered.

Along with Kejriwal, the other AAP politicians whose names appear in the investigating reports of CBI and the Enforcement Directorate (ED) are Satyendar Jain, Manish Sisodia, Sanjay Singh, and Raghav Chadha.

In his videos, the Punjab leader Bittu said that AAP politician Raghav Chadha, who was adopted by Kejriwal as his son, is absconding after looting Punjab's money which needs to be recovered.

In fact, Bittu is not alone who is complaining about massive corruption – including liquor scam – in Punjab. It is believed that a few Punjab AAP politicians led by CM Bhagwant Mann may be arrested and jailed as Kejriwal's shady Delhi liquor policy is being implemented in Punjab also.

In November last year, a Punjab Congress leader Navjot Singh Sidhu [filed a complaint](#) to the Punjab Governor against the Punjab Government led by Bhagwant Mann. In his complaint letter, Sidhu raised concerns over the precarious financial situation in Punjab,

deteriorating law and order in the state, and lack of accountability in the Bhagwant Mann government.

Moreover, the president of the Shiromani Akali Dal (SAD) Sukhbir Singh Badal also urged the Punjab Governor to hold a [probe](#) into the alleged Rs. 500-crore liquor policy scam committed by the AAP government in the state. It is learnt that the investigating agencies have already started [questioning](#) some of the Punjab Government functionaries and AAP leaders to know the extent of corruption in the Punjab liquor scandal.

While AAP politicians are apparently involved in multiple [corruption scandals](#), it is expected that some of them named above will soon be behind bars. In September last year, the CBI launched a [preliminary inquiry](#) into alleged irregularities in the construction and renovation of Kejriwal's house on which the public money in excess of Rs. 45 crore has been squandered. It is a case of misappropriation of public money – which is a serious financial crime allegedly committed by Kejriwal.

Moreover, reports [suggest](#) that the ED dragnet will soon extend to more AAP leaders including Atishi, Raghav Chadha, Saurabh Bhardwaj, and Durgesh Pathak. Some of these [names](#) are already in the files of the ED or the CBI.

Also, on April 2, the ED [accused](#) AAP leaders of bribery and corruption in the Delhi Jal Board (DJB) scam, claiming that AAP used the corruption money as election funds. And, in May, Delhi LG V. K. Saxena [ordered a probe](#) by the National Investigation Agency (NIA) to investigate Kejriwal's links with terror outfits.

Since a number of AAP politicians in Punjab and Delhi are allegedly involved in a series of financial crimes, in May 2024, the ED [named](#) the entire Aam Aadmi Party as accused in the liquor scam. Now to mislead the public, Kejriwal, his wife, and AAP politicians are falsely blaming PM Narendra Modi and his Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP) for Kejriwal's imprisonment.

While courts believe that Kejriwal has a distinct role in Delhi liquor scandal and other crimes, the dishonest AAP leaders are holding protests against Modi and BJP with the help of unknown people who are believed to be hired for protests.

Moreover, it appears that Kejriwal is also paying crores of rupees of public money to some [greedy lawyers](#) who try to protect him and other AAP leaders unscrupulously in courts. The bail cases of Kejriwal or other AAP leaders are listed so frequently in Indian

courts that it appears all the courts are working only to decide AAP cases and the bails for the party's leaders.

Since Kejriwal is not supposed to spend public money to defend AAP corruption cases, it is a form of corruption that Kejriwal commits in collusion with dishonest lawyers – particularly who belong to the Congress party.

In May 2024, I filed an [application](#) under the Right to Information (RTI) Act to know the amount of money being paid for legal services to protect Kejriwal and other AAP leaders in courts. I have not yet received the response. With their apparent involvement in a number of crime and corruption cases, it will be a travesty of justice if Kejriwal or any of his jailed AAP colleagues are released on bail for the next few years.

In fact, if the courts and investigating agencies probe all the cases diligently, it is possible that Kejriwal and many other AAP leaders will have to spend their remaining lives in jail.

NATIONAL HERALD CORRUPTION CASE

The Delhi High Court has asked Congress leaders Rahul Gandhi and Sonia Gandhi - along with petitioner Subramanian Swamy - to file a short note on the submissions in the National Herald case. According to a *Business Standard* [report](#) of July 22, 2024, Justice Neena Bansal Krishna directed them to file the written note on the arguments along with a fee of Rs. 15,000 within four weeks and listed the matter for arguments on October 29, 2024.

The high court was hearing a petition filed by Swamy who sought to lead evidence before the trial court in the National Herald case, in which the Gandhis and a few other Congress leaders are accused. The *Business Standard* report adds that on February 22, 2021, the court had issued notice to the Gandhis, All India Congress Committee (AICC) general secretary Oscar Fernandes (since died), Suman Dubey, Sam Pitroda, and Young Indian (YI), to seek their response on Swamy's plea and stayed the proceedings in the case. The court said on July 22 that the interim order of stay shall continue till the next date of hearing in the matter.

The Enforcement Directorate (ED) of India – which investigates financial crimes – had asked Congress leader Rahul Gandhi to appear before it on June 13, 2022 for questioning in a money laundering case. Earlier, he was called on June 2. Since Rahul Gandhi was out of the country, he had asked for a revised date. His mother Sonia Gandhi was asked to appear in this case on June 8, 2022.

Both Congress leaders were being questioned by ED in the money laundering case linked to the National Herald newspaper. The probe agency recorded the statements of Congress leaders under criminal sections of the Prevention of Money Laundering Act (PMLA) for the alleged financial irregularities in their closely held company, Young Indian.

The National Herald is published by Associated Journals Limited (AJL) and owned by Young Indian. Although Congress claims that it is a fabricated case in which its top leaders are being implicated, the party has not given any explicit proof of their innocence. In 2018, the Delhi High Court had dismissed the petition filed by AJL linked with Congress and observed that the order passed by the government justifies the re-entry of the premises at 5-A, Bahadur Shah Zafar Marg, New Delhi.

According to a statement released by India's Ministry of Housing & Urban Affairs, the court has further ordered that there is no impediment in the way of the government to invoke the provisions of PP Act [The Public Premises (Eviction of Unauthorised Occupants) Act, 1971] to seek eviction and vacant possession of the property within a period of two weeks by 03.01.2019.

The case – filed by an Indian politician Subramanian Swamy against Congress leaders Sonia Gandhi and her son Rahul Gandhi, and others – is known as the National Herald (newspaper) corruption case. The government statement added that 0.3365 acre of land was allotted to AJL in Delhi in 1962-63 at a concessional rate of Rs. 1,25,000 per acre for construction of a five-story building (in addition to basement) for the purpose of press on the ground floor and offices on other floors.

However, according to the statement, complaints were received regarding misuse of the land. It was found by the inspecting team of the ministry on April 9, 2018 that no printing press was functioning at any floor of the premises and no paper stock was found anywhere. In earlier inspection also, the basement where the press machine should have been, was found vacant. Further, the statement adds that it was also found that almost all shares of AJL were transferred to Young Indian having the same address as that of AJL without any permission of the ministry.

As per a report of Income Tax Department, in Young Indian company, majority of shares (76%) are held by the Gandhi family and the rest by other Congress leaders Motilal Vora and Oscar Fernandes. It was also observed that instead of using the land given to AJL for press purposes, they are earning a huge sum of money by renting out almost the entire

building except one floor which has negated the purpose for which the land was originally allotted.

Since all these violations came to the notice of the government, Show Cause Notices were issued to AJL on June 18, 2018 and again on September 24, 2018. As AJL could not give any satisfactory reply to these violations, an order for re-entry of the premises was issued by the ministry on October 30, 2018. Against this order, the AJL had gone to the Delhi High Court which pronounced its order in December 2018.

As per the complaint filed in the court of the Metropolitan Magistrate, AJL took an interest-free loan of Rs. 90.25 crore from the Congress party. It is alleged that the loan was not repaid. A closely held company, Young Indian, was incorporated in November 2010 with a capital of Rs. 50 lakh and it acquired almost all the shareholding of AJL and all its properties (alleged to be worth Rs. 5,000 crore).

Subramanian Swamy had alleged criminal misappropriation by both Sonia Gandhi and Rahul Gandhi. The courts had determined that a prima facie case was established in the matter.

POLITICIANS FACING CORRUPTION CHARGES JOIN BJP TO GET ACQUITTED: REPORT

A new report finds that a slew of opposition politicians joined the Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP) of prime minister (PM) Narendra Modi to get acquitted in corruption cases, as the Modi government controls the central investigating agencies. Since 2014 when Modi became the PM, according to the [report](#) compiled by *The Indian Express*, 25 opposition leaders facing corruption investigations joined BJP and 23 of them got reprieve.

According to the report, the opposition politicians who joined BJP to get acquitted belong to different political outfits: 10 from Congress; four each from Nationalist Congress Party (NCP) and Shiv Sena; three from All India Trinamool Congress (TMC); two from Telugu Desam Party (TDP); and one each from Samajwadi Party (SP) and Yuvajana Sramika Rythu Congress Party (YSRCP).

The Indian Express [report](#) released on April 4, 2024 reveals that six of the politicians from opposition parties moved to the BJP this year alone, weeks before the Lok Sabha election which was scheduled to take place from April 19. The leaders named in the report include Ajit Pawar, Praful Patel, Ashok Chavan, Himanta Biswa Sarma, Suwendu Adhikari, Pratap Sarnaik, Hasan Mushrif, Bhavana Gawali, and others. Opposition parties

allege that the Modi government (which is in fact Modi alone because he works like a dictator) misuses the central agencies such as the Enforcement Directorate (ED), Central Bureau of Investigation (CBI), and the Income Tax Department to terrorize the opposition parties so that they do not raise their voice against the wrongdoings of the Modi regime. [You can [click here](#) to read this article in Hindi.]

AN EXPRESS INVESTIGATION

Since 2014, 25 Opposition leaders facing corruption probe crossed over to BJP, 23 of them got reprieve

3 cases closed, 20 stalled; officials say probe is open, will act if required

DEEPTIMAN TIWARY
NEW DELHI, APRIL 2

THE LAW takes its own course — unless it is nudged by politics. Since 2014, as many as 25 prominent politicians facing action from Central agencies for alleged corruption have crossed over to the BJP. They cut across party lines: 10 are from the Congress; four each from NCP and Shiv Sena; three from TMC; two from TDP; and one each from SP and YSRCP. In 23 of these cases, their political move has translated into reprieve, an investigation by the Indian Express has found. Three of the cases have been closed; 20 others remain stalled or in cold storage — the investigative agency's action, after the switch, has been, in fact, inaction. Six of the politicians on this list moved to the BJP this year alone, weeks before the general elections. This is in sharp contrast to what happens when the accused is in the Opposition — an investigation by the Indian Express in 2022 revealed how 85 per cent of prominent politicians at the Enforcement Directorate (ED) and Central Bureau of Investigation (CBI) took action against after 2014, when the NDA came to power, were from the Opposition. The Opposition calls it the "washing machine," the mechanism by which politicians accused of corruption don't face legal consequences if they quit their party and join the BJP. Not that this is new — it's the scale that is unprecedented.

CONTINUED ON PAGE 6

PROBE PIVOTS ON POLITICAL FLIP-FLOPS IN AJIT PAWAR CASE **P 6**

Pawar, Patel, Adhikari, Sarma... how some cases were closed, others sent to cold storage

DEEPTIMAN TIWARY
NEW DELHI, APRIL 2

FROM CLOSING the case to putting it in cold storage — this is how the Enforcement Directorate, CBI and IT Department changed course once the accused changed their party, and moved over to the ruling BJP, reveals an investigation of the chronology of case records by The Indian Express.

CLOSING THE CASE
AJIT PAWAR: Mumbai probe shut, case his dead-end
Party Shift: NCP, shifted to BJP-led NDA in 2023.
The Case: The Economic Offences Wing (EOW)'s FIR against Ajit Pawar, Sharad Pawar and others, in a case of money laundering linked to alleged irregularities in Maharashtra State Cooperative Bank, was based on a Bombay High Court order of August 2019. The ED's probe that followed also named Congress leaders Jantn Patil, Diliprao Deshmukh and the late Madan Patil; NCP's Ishwarlal Jain and Shivaji Rao Nalawade; and Shiv Sena's Anantkumar Adulkar.

CHRONOLOGY OF FLIP-FLOP
August 2019: Mumbai Police's EOW registers FIR against Pawar.
September 2019: ED begins probe based on FIR.
October 2020: EOW files closure report. ED challenges it.
April 2022: ED files chargesheet without naming Pawar.
June 2022: Sena splits, Shinde faction forms NDA govt with BJP.
July 2022: Pawar joins NDA govt as Dy CM.
January 2024: EOW files second closure report.
Current Status: ED has filed intervention application in court on EOW's closure.

PRAPUL PATEL: Safe landing after turbulences
Party Shift: NCP, shifted to BJP-led NDA in 2023.
The Case: The former civil aviation minister is being probed by CBI and ED for alleged corruption in the purchase of 113 aircraft by Air India as well as in the AI-Indian Airlines merger. The allegations involve ceding of profitable routes to foreign airlines, opening of training institutes with foreign investment, and ties with lobbyist Deepak Talwar. The FIRs do not list Patel as an accused but mention his name.

CHRONOLOGY OF FLIP-FLOP
May 2017: CBI files FIRs in Air India-Indian Airlines merger.
May 2019: ED names Patel in its chargesheet.
June 2022: Patel joins NDA.
March 2024: CBI files closure report.
Current Status: Closure pending in court.

CONTINUED ON PAGE 6

Another report of March 22, 2024 in *The Indian Express* [showed](#) that between 2014 and September 2022, 121 prominent political leaders came under the ED radar while 115 of them were from the opposition parties. Although Modi falsely claims that he is working to weed out corruption from the country, it is being observed that Modi and his government have crossed all limits of corruption and malfeasance.

The [electoral bonds scam](#), for example, reveals that Modi's BJP is the largest beneficiary of this clandestine corruption fund. Electoral bonds are among the instruments of bribe that big corporates use to secretly fund political parties in quid pro quo deals.

In many cases of corruption by the Modi regime, courts and investigating agencies turn a blind eye to absolve

Modi and his friends because court judges and investigating officers work as slaves in the Modi empire. [*Photo: The Indian Express Report: 25 opposition leaders facing corruption investigations joined BJP and 23 of them got reprieve.*]

In the Adani case, for example, the [Supreme Court](#) deceptively exonerated the Adani Group in the money laundering and accounting fraud case because oligarch Gautam Adani is a partner of PM Modi. In fact, the Modi-Adani collusion case is termed as the

Modani (portmanteau for Modi and Adani) corruption scandal, which is perhaps the biggest grand corruption crime in the history of mankind.

The other corruption cases in which the Indian judiciary succumbed and dishonestly protected the Modi regime include PM-CARES Fund [case](#), Rafale corruption [case](#), Sri Lanka energy project [case](#) involving Adani Group, Modi-Adani [collusion](#) case, Sahara-Birla payoff [case](#), Predator Drone [deal](#), and a number of other [cases](#) in which Modi's party colleagues are allegedly involved. Since Modi has been misusing the agencies to arrest and incarcerate opposition leaders, some of them who are actually involved in corruption and money laundering rackets, claim that the cases against them are politically motivated.

As the Modi regime is [founded](#) on crime and corruption, it does not allow the investigating agencies to work independently. While most agencies are defunct, Modi blatantly violates constitutional norms to appoint [former judges](#) and officials with tainted records to head top offices.

For example, a former Supreme Court judge Ajay Manikrao Khanwilkar has been appointed as the [chairperson](#) of India's top anti-corruption ombudsman Lokpal. After retiring from the Supreme Court in July 2022, Khanwilkar has been rewarded with the plum position at the Lokpal office largely because of his judgments in favour of Modi or the Modi regime.

JUSTICE KHANWILKAR WITH DUBIOUS RECORD APPOINTED TO HEAD ANTI-CORRUPTION OUTFIT LOKPAL

A former Supreme Court judge Ajay Manikrao Khanwilkar has been appointed as the chairperson of India's top anti-corruption ombudsman Lokpal. His [appointment](#) was announced on February 27, 2024 - after keeping the Lokpal chairperson's position vacant for about two years.

Khanwilkar was handpicked by a committee comprising prime minister (PM) Narendra Modi, Chief Justice of India (CJI) D.Y. Chandrachud, and Leader of the Opposition in Lok Sabha, Adhir Ranjan Chowdhury. After retiring from the Supreme Court in July 2022, Khanwilkar has been rewarded with the plum position at the Lokpal office largely because of his [judgments](#) in favour of Modi or the Modi regime.

As a member of a 2022 bench, Justice Khanwilkar dubiously dismissed a plea of Zakia Jafri to exonerate Modi who was the prime accused in the Gujarat massacre of 2002 in

which thousands of people - mainly Muslims - were murdered. Zakia Jafri - the wife of MP Ehsan Jafri who was murdered in the Gujarat riots - had challenged the Special Investigation Team's (SIT) clean chit to 64 people, including Modi who was the chief minister of Gujarat when the pogrom happened. The 2023 BBC [documentary](#) 'India: The Modi Question' sheds light on Modi's role in Gujarat violence.

Khanwilkar not only dismissed Jafri's petition, but also pronounced the hostile judgment that was used by the Gujarat Police on the following day to arrest activist Teesta Setalvad and former IPS officer R. B. Sreekumar on charges of fabricating evidence linked to the Gujarat riots.

In 2022, with another judgment to help the Modi regime, Khanwilkar while heading a three-judge bench upheld the Foreign Contribution (Regulation) Amendment Act, 2020 to regulate NGOs' access to foreign donors.

The Modi government has frequently attacked NGOs and civil society organizations through draconian FCRA regulations so that they do not criticize the government's autocratic actions.

As the opposition parties often complain that Modi misuses the agencies such as the Enforcement Directorate (ED) to target his opponents, in 2022 Khanwilkar - with a controversial judgment - enhanced ED's powers under the Prevention of Money Laundering Act (PMLA).

Khanwilkar's unscrupulous record as a Supreme Court judge is being widely denounced on [social media](#) by people. As post-retirement benefits to judges influence their pre-retirement judgments, Khanwilkar is a beneficiary of this evil trend.

Corrupt Judiciary

But Khanwilkar is not alone who has been gifted for his blind loyalty to the Modi regime. A former Chief Justice of India (CJI) Ranjan Gogoi was [rewarded](#) with membership of Rajya Sabha, the upper house of India's parliament. With his bias toward the Modi government, Gogoi – who retired in November 2019 – was largely working as a government spokesperson.

During his tenure, he had completely tarnished the image of the Supreme Court which had been reduced to the level of a party office of Modi's Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP). As

a judge, Gogoi was pronouncing judgments such as the Ayodhya verdict and decision on the [Rafale corruption](#) case to meet Modi's expectations.

Similarly, a former Supreme Court judge, Justice Arun Kumar Mishra, was handpicked in 2021 by the Modi government for the post of National Human Rights Commission (NHRC) chairperson because of his sycophancy for Modi. While Mishra does not have any record in the human rights sphere, he was selected despite strong opposition to his selection.

Senior Congress leader and Leader of Opposition in Rajya Sabha Mallikarjun Kharge – who was a member of the selection committee – dissociated himself from the process of NHRC chairperson's selection. "In my letter to PM Modi, I raised concerns regarding the manner in which the NHRC appointments were made," Kharge [wrote](#) in his tweet on June 2, 2021. He added that Mishra's appointment smacks of partisanship and quid pro quo. "I strongly condemn this," Kharge stated.

Mishra had retired from the Supreme Court in September 2020 and during his tenure he pronounced many wrong [judgements](#) to please Modi and brazenly admired him presumably to grab a lucrative position after retirement. [You can [click here](#) to read *How Justice Arun Mishra Rose to Become the Most Influential Judge in the Supreme Court*]

Speaking at the International Judicial Conference in 2020, Justice Mishra had described Modi as an "internationally acclaimed visionary", and praised his "versatile genius to think globally and act locally." Mishra's remarks were so shameful that the Supreme Court Bar Association (SCBA) had to issue a resolution to denounce his admiration for Modi while the judges are supposed to maintain a safe distance from politicians. In its statement, the SCBA said it has taken note with deep sense of anguish and concern the statement made by Mishra to praise Modi.

The SCBA, according to the [statement](#), also expressed that such proximity and familiarity may impact the decision making process by the judges and may give rise to justifiable doubts in the minds of the litigants about the outcome.

As a journalist and human rights defender, in October 2023, I [filed a petition](#) at the Human Rights Council Branch of the Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights to remove and prosecute Mishra.

In another case, a retired [judge](#) Surendra Kumar Yadav, who gave the verdict in the controversial Babri mosque demolition case in 2020, was given the lucrative up-Lokayukta (deputy Lokayukta) [position](#) in Uttar Pradesh in 2021. The office of

Lokayukta is an anti-corruption [authority](#) that investigates cases related to corruption, government mismanagement, or abuse of power by public servants or ministers.

In fact, in all autocratic regimes that work under the garb of democratic systems, the rulers silently use courts to impose their own decisions on citizens and suppress all kinds of dissent.

Rampant Corruption in Modi Regime

Earlier, K.V. Chowdary – who had retired as the Central Vigilance Commissioner (CVC) which is India's top anti-corruption organization – was [hired](#) as additional director on the board of Reliance Industries Limited (RIL) led by Mukesh Ambani.

Ambani is a close capitalist friend of Modi, who has been embroiled in multiple corruption scandals. As the CVC of India, Chowdary intervened to get all investigations against Modi dropped.

As the Modi government has given top administrative and judicial posts to its own loyal men who could cover up the crime and corruption cases in which top BJP politicians including Modi are involved, there was a huge controversy over the manner the previous Lokpal Justice Pinaki Chandra Ghose was appointed.

Multiple reports suggest that the entire exercise of the [appointment](#) of Lokpal was held in a shady manner and Lokpal was ignoring the corruption cases of top politicians and bureaucrats in the Modi regime.

Since the Lokpal office under Justice Pinaki Chandra Ghose was causing serious harm to the citizens of India, people protested against its poor performance. An online petition exposed the corruption at Lokpal office which is supposed to stop corruption in the country. The petition asserted that the Lokpal officials are squandering huge public money without any accountability.

Available on an American public petition website, the 2022 [petition](#) argues that the Lokpal office has completely failed to check corruption and it has become a senior citizens' club. Since the Lokpal performance has been pathetic, people have stopped filing their complaints to the anti-corruption ombudsman.

The petition urged the Lokpal bureaucrats that if they are not able to perform, they must resign from their positions. Moreover, in 2022, I sent a [petition](#) to the President and the

Chief Justice of India with the appeal to remove Lokpal Justice Pinaki Chandra Ghose under charges of non-performance and dereliction of duty.

Recently, another Judge A.K. Vishvesha has been appointed as Lokpal of Dr. Shakuntala Misra National Rehabilitation University, Lucknow, for his immoral [judgment](#) on Gyanvapi Mosque.

His judgment that favoured the anti-Muslim Hindutava agenda of the Modi regime permitted the family of a late priest the right to resume 'pooja' in the southern cellar of the Gyanvapi Mosque after three decades. Astonishingly, Vishvesha passed the judgment on his last working day as a district judge on January 31, 2024.

Dishonest Supreme Court Judges

The judges - particularly of the Supreme Court - deliver weekend academic lectures on constitution, democracy, and justice. But they do not practice in courts what they preach in their academic discourse. All that they say is [meaningless rhetoric](#) because when they sit in their courts as judges, they leave no stone unturned to crush democracy and violate all norms of the constitution.

It has been seen in multiple cases during the past few years. The judges in high courts and lower courts are so naive that they cannot even deliver lectures on law and justice while their court decisions are mostly wrong. Since the corrupt judges in the Supreme Court and other courts of India expect post-retirement positions and other benefits, they work lawlessly in courts as agents of the Modi regime. As a result, corruption has been increasing exponentially in India.

In its global [report](#) released in January 2024, Transparency International notes that corruption is increasing in those countries which are experiencing a decline in the functioning of justice systems. In this context, it cites the [Rule of Law Index](#) of the World Justice Project, which confirms the deteriorating justice delivery system in India.

According to the latest 2023 Rule of Law Index, India's [score](#) declined from 0.50 in 2022 to 0.49 in 2023 and India ranked 79th across 142 countries in 2023 while the civil and criminal justice systems in the country are on the verge of collapse. The World Justice Project findings are consistent with the incidents of increasing judicial corruption in India.

While India is already a majoritarian [nation](#), a senior advocate and former president of Supreme Court Bar Association, Dushyant Dave, observes that the judiciary in India has

also become a “majoritarian judiciary.” In an [interview](#) on January 28, 2024 with *LiveLaw* news service, Dave said that the judiciary – including the Supreme Court – is remaining silent while several transgressions of law are taking place at the instance of the Executive (Modi regime). These transgressions by the judiciary are also being seen in corruption cases where the judges are complicit in state crimes.

There are numerous reports of corruption in the Indian judiciary, but most corruption cases have been brushed under the carpet. In 2022, the Supreme Court [dropped](#) a contempt case against lawyer-activist Prashant Bhushan who tried to expose corruption in the judiciary with his interview given to a local magazine. Under pressure from the top court, he issued an apology in a convoluted language to get the contempt proceedings against him stopped.

However, the same Prashant Bhushan - who practices in the Supreme Court - kept talking about judicial corruption in open public forums. For example, in his speech at a seminar, Prashant Bhushan alludes to a Rs. 9 crore bribe to the Chief Justice when talking about judicial corruption in India. While it is difficult to directly prove the payment of bribes to judges, there is enough circumstantial evidence which can be drawn from their conduct and judgments that they pronounce in favour of certain politicians or affluent parties. [You can [click here](#) to watch that video of Prashant Bhushan about judicial corruption and the bad state of Indian judiciary.]

Moreover, a slew of former Supreme Court judges - particularly Justice Madan B. Lokur - is delivering [lectures](#) to expose the unethical working in the top court and other courts of India. And leading Supreme Court lawyers and judges are also revealing the cases of massive corruption in the Indian judiciary. In a TV [interview](#), a former judge of the Supreme Court Markandey Katju explained rampant corruption in the Indian judiciary and described how politicians influence court judges to get acquitted.

Since corruption is a white-collar financial crime, it is not essential to show the exchange of money in the form of kickbacks or bribes to prove a crime. Only circumstantial evidence in terms of delinquency or misconduct of a judge is required to prosecute them. However, the vigilance committees of courts do not follow this fundamental principle of evidence and acquit the accused judges - sometimes without even holding a proper investigation.

As a journalist and anti-corruption activist, I had filed a complaint in the Supreme Court against Manish Khurana as AD&SJ-cum-P.O., Appellate Tribunal - MCD, Tis Hazari Courts,

Delhi, for his involvement in a massive citywide construction-cum-corruption scandal. As my complaint was forwarded to Delhi High Court, the Registrar Vigilance of Delhi High Court held a video conference with me in July 2023 to record my statement.

I had submitted multiple exhibits, photographs, facts, and video links along with my 32-page complaint against judge Manish Khurana. However, I was informed by the Delhi High Court that some unnamed Vigilance Committee judges closed the corruption case of judge Manish Khurana without even informing him and without allowing me to participate in the prosecution process to prove his crime. [You can [click here](#) to download and read the complaint dated September 3, 2023: *Flawed decision in the judicial corruption case of judge Mr. Manish Khurana.*]

As the so-called vigilance committee judges provide impunity to the accused judicial officers, it shows their complicity in crime. In their wrongful decisions, they do not even take into account the anti-corruption laws.

Corruption Cases in Modi Government

Since judges are corrupt, they do not take action against corrupt bureaucrats and politicians. In the Adani case, for example, the [Supreme Court](#) deceptively exonerated the Adani Group in the money laundering and accounting fraud case because oligarch Gautam Adani is a partner of PM Modi.

In fact, the Modi-Adani collusion case is termed as the Modani (portmanteau for Modi and Adani) corruption scandal, which is perhaps the biggest grand corruption crime in the history of mankind.

The other corruption cases in which the Indian judiciary succumbed and dishonestly protected the Modi regime include PM-CARES Fund [case](#), Rafale corruption [case](#), Sri Lanka energy project [case](#) involving Adani Group, Modi-Adani [collusion](#) case, Sahara-Birla payoff [case](#), Predator Drone [deal](#), and a number of other [cases](#) in which Modi's party colleagues are allegedly involved.

Now, as Khanwilkar's unethical record shows, he will also not take any steps to stop corruption in the Modi regime. Rather, as the Lokpal chairperson he is also expected to provide impunity to Modi and other corrupt functionaries in his government.

According to a February 28 [report](#) in *The Indian Express*, the [government](#) has also appointed six members, including three judicial members, to the Lokpal. Former

Himachal Pradesh High Court Chief Justice Lingappa Narayana Swamy, former Allahabad High Court Chief Justice Sanjay Yadav, and former Karnataka High Court Chief Justice and Law Commission Chairperson Ritu Raj Awasthi are judicial members.

The non-judicial members are former Chief Election Commissioner Sushil Chandra, former Chief Secretary of Gujarat Pankaj Kumar, and former Rural Development Secretary Ajay Tirkey. The Lokpal chairperson and the members are appointed for a term of five years or serve till they attain the age of 70 years, whichever is earlier.

CABINET SECRETARIAT PROVIDES IMPUNITY TO CORRUPT IAS OFFICERS

Despite repeated reminders from the Department of Personnel and Training (DoPT), the Cabinet Secretariat is not taking action against IAS officers who are involved in a citywide construction-cum-corruption racket under the lethal [floor area ratio](#) (FAR) scheme in occupied housing societies of Delhi. Their present positions are now known. According to the DoPT Office Memorandums, the names of the IAS officers who are facing corruption investigations are given below:

Mr. Anurag Jain, IAS (MP: 1989), former Vice Chairman, Delhi Development Authority (DDA), and currently Secretary, Department for Promotion of Industry and Internal Trade, Ministry of Commerce & Industry

Mr. Tarun Kapoor, IAS (HP: 1987), former Vice Chairman, DDA, and Retd., Secretary M/o Petroleum and Natural Gas

Mr. Pankaj Kumar, IAS (AGMUT:2012), District Magistrate (North-East) Delhi

Mr. Devinder Singh, IAS (AGMUT:2003). former Registrar Cooperative Societies (RCS), Delhi Government

Mr. Devesh Singh, IAS (AGMUT: 2008), Registrar Cooperative Societies (RCS), Delhi Government

Mr. Manish Kumar Gupta, IAS (AGMUT: 1991), Vice Chairman, DDA

Mr. Sanjeev Khirwar, IAS (AGMUT:1994), former Chairman, Delhi Pollution Control Committee (DPCC), Government of NCT of Delhi, Delhi

Mr. Virendra Kumar, IAS (AGMUT: 2005), former Registrar Cooperative Societies (RCS), Delhi Government

Ms. Garima Gupta, IAS (AGMUT:2004), former Secretary (Cooperation), Delhi Government

Mr. Tanmay Kumar, IAS (RJ: 1993), Additional Secretary, M/o Environment, Forest and Climate Change

Although these IAS officers have come in the law-enforcement dragnet, their accomplices such as junior government officers at Delhi Development Authority (DDA), the office of Registrar Cooperative Societies (RCS), police officers, local criminals in housing societies, and builders' mafia members have not yet been caught.

[You can [click here](#) to read the related report dated July 21, 2024 with DoPT letters.]

I have also approached different other authorities to get these IAS officers prosecuted and punished. As I had filed the complaint on the Public Grievance Monitoring System (PGMS) of Delhi Government under Grievance No. 2024060654 dated July 21, 2024, the PGMS status on August 23, 2024 showed that my complaint is being pushed from one department to another but the careless government officials have not taken any action against the accused IAS officers. [You can [click here](#) to download and study the PGMS document.]

I had also filed the complaint against these IAS officers at the office of the Central Vigilance Commission (CVC) of India. The CVC office says, "Your complaint 39336/2023 has been examined and taken up for detailed investigation by the CVO, MINISTRY OF HOME AFFAIRS. Based on the investigation report, suitable action will be taken by the competent authority." This is the complaint status as of August 24, 2024. But so far no action has been taken. [You can [click here](#) to read the CVC response.]

As I have been struggling for years to get the dangerous FAR construction stopped, this case of citywide corruption-cum-construction scandal is also available on PGMS under Grievance No. 2021120462 dated 14.10.2021 along with a number of additional documents with evidence that reveal massive crime and corruption in this case. Instead of providing parawise responses to the facts stated in my comprehensive complaints, the accused officials are trying to get the cases against them closed by repeating their brief, misleading, and false responses.

[You can [click here](#) to know the details of the complaints including the names of more accused officials who are trying to close the cases on PGMS with a criminal intent.]

Crime, Corruption, and Impunity in India

Politicians, bureaucrats, police, and judges have formed a criminal gang in India. The following cases depict how they collude with criminals and commit crimes and corruption with impunity while the ordinary citizens are suffering.

Click the following links for details.

Delhi Cooperative Tribunal Case ^{New}	Delhi IAS Case
Threats for Editorial Work ^{New}	Judicial Corruption Case ^{New}
Grand Corruption Case	Manipur Violence Case (Protected)
UN Petition on Punjab Unrest	RCS-EOW Case
Cabinet Secretariat Case	Ministry of Home Affairs (MHA) Case
Prime Minister Office (PMO) Case	Delhi Lokayukta Case
DoPT Case	CBI Case
Economic Offences Wing (EOW) Case	Supreme Court Case
Delhi Govt Case	Delhi Petitions Committee / CVC Case
NHRC Case	Petition on School Education
Environmental Crime Case	Lokpal Removal Case
Judicial System Abuse Case	RCS Corruption Case
Lokayukta Delhi Corruption Case	Widehouse Scandal
NHRC Case at UN HRC	IAS Group Corruption Case
CPGRAMS Cases	PGMS Cases
IAS Corruption Record	UNCAC Petition
Delhi Police Case	DoPT Processes
RCS RTI Violations	DDA Corruption Case
U.S. Case Report	UN Human Rights Petition
Failure of Legal Aid System	Amendment to DCS Act

Petitions and Representations by Rakesh Raman. Up to August 2024

CORRUPTION MAKES INDIA A CRIMINALIZED KLEPTOCRACY

Today, because of increasing corruption, India is facing the worst existential crisis as the country's 1.4 billion commoners are under a grave threat from their own political rulers who have been exploiting them for the past over seven decades after India got independence from the Britishers in 1947.

While almost all Indian politicians are crooks and corrupt – many are facing serious criminal charges – they have been winning elections by dividing voters on the basis of their caste, creed, color, and religious affiliations. They have also been tampering with electronic voting machines ([EVMs](#)) and bribing the voters to win elections fraudulently.

Now, there is a dangerous nexus between these dishonest politicians who want to stay in power by hook or by crook and cunning capitalists who are silently looting the Indian public. Together, they have reduced India to a level of [criminalized kleptocracy](#), in which all the four pillars of democracy have collapsed. The courts in India have lost their relevance, bureaucrats are extremely corrupt, while the police and security forces operate as gangs of criminals.

Political and bureaucratic corruption is the main cause of poverty, pollution, sickness, and hunger in India. Political corruption is so extreme that it is difficult to measure it. However, estimates exist for bureaucratic corruption in the country.

In the [book](#) '*Corruption in India: The DNA and the RNA*' authored by Bibek Debroy and Laveesh Bhandari, it is said that the public officials in India may be cornering as much as Rs. 92,122 crore (\$18.42 billion), or 1.26% of the GDP, through corruption. The book estimates that corruption is increasing in India by over 100% annually, and most bribery is accrued from the transport industry, real estate, and other public services.

In 2019, the bureaucratic corruption in India through bribery, policy distortion, delinquency, process violation, red-tapism, tax terrorism, etc. was estimated to be \$100 billion. The ill-gotten money with Indian politicians is believed to be in excess of \$1 trillion. Data [reveals](#) that many of the biggest scandals have involved high level government officials and top politicians. These include the 2010 Commonwealth Games scam (US\$10 billion), unresolved Rafale [scam](#) (US\$4 billion), the Adarsh Housing Society scam, the Coal Mining scam (US\$23 billion), the Mining Scandal in Karnataka, [Delhi liquor scandal](#), and the Cash for Vote scams.

Clean House: Free Anti-Corruption Service

The free anti-corruption service “Clean House” runs as a [community court](#) to report about crime and corruption happening in Delhi’s cooperative group housing societies (CGHS). These societies - where millions of people live - have become dangerous centers of crime and corruption.

The corruption in these housing complexes is being committed by the management committee (MC) members or administrators in connivance with the corrupt officials of Registrar Cooperative Societies (RCS) of Delhi Government, Delhi Development Authority (DDA), Delhi Police, Municipal Corporation of Delhi (MCD), Delhi Fire Service (DFS), Delhi Pollution Control Committee (DPCC), and a few other departments.

The “Clean House” service allows the harassed residents of Delhi to register their complaints through an [online form](#) and the case reports are shared with the government departments so that people's grievances could be addressed and they could live in a corruption-free environment.

Since most Delhi Government politicians and bureaucrats are highly corrupt, they usually ignore the public complaints.

12 STEPS TO DEAL WITH CORRUPTION IN INDIA

In order to avert a situation of imminent civil unrest because of corruption in the country, the judiciary and law-enforcement agencies must take the following 12 preventive steps – at least.

1. As today’s online interfaces for the public to file corruption complaints are very weak and ineffective, robust technology-based online interfaces must be established to monitor and address the corruption complaints in a time-bound manner.
2. The services of government officials who are slow in response to the public or who are not following the statutory procedures must be terminated immediately.

- 3.** When the prima facie case is established and any inquiry is ordered, the corrupt government officials must be jailed for their criminality while the onus should be on them to prove their innocence.
- 4.** The members of the public who complain against corruption should not be harassed by asking them to furnish documentary evidence because no documentary evidence is required in white-collar crimes such as fraud or corruption. Only circumstantial evidence in terms of non-compliance of statutory procedures should be enough to prosecute and punish the wrongdoers.
- 5.** As it is not possible for most complainants to approach the conventional courts, it is the responsibility of the administration (politicians and bureaucrats) to provide speedy justice to the suffering people. This should be part of the essential governance.
- 6.** While dereliction of duty is also a crime, the inefficient and delinquent officials must be indicted and suspended from their jobs.
- 7.** The government has no right to show a public complaint as disposed of by simply sending it to some other department or giving a perfunctory reply to the complainant. A complaint can be disposed of only when the justice is fully delivered as asked by the complainant.
- 8.** A single case of corruption can harm hundreds or thousands of lives. Therefore, in the courts, corruption should be considered equivalent to crimes such as culpable homicide, attempt to murder, or even murder in some cases.
- 9.** The names of government officials and politicians who are facing any kind of corruption inquiry must be openly put on exclusive websites created for each State and Central government offices.
- 10.** In order to ensure transparency of inquiries, all the communications exchanged between the accused and the inquiry officers should be made publicly available on the websites.
- 11.** The hearings in corruption cases of bureaucrats and politicians must be on-camera public hearings which must also be live-streamed in real time.
- 12.** In extreme cases of bureaucratic and political corruption, public execution should be the punishment for the culprits.

Untrained Anti-Corruption Officers in India

One of the main reasons for increasing corruption in India is the lack of skills among the investigating officers. While the anti-corruption laws are good in the country, the law-enforcement officials cannot even read or properly interpret those laws.

Most officials think that bribery is the only form of corruption and they force the complainants to prove the transaction of bribe money. However, in the white-collar crimes such as corruption and fraud, the bribe money is not quite visible.

If a government official is not performing his or her duties responsibly or not following the prescribed processes, it is a clear case of corruption. Bureaucratic inefficiency or carelessness is a serious form of corruption. After getting the prima facie evidence, the anti-corruption agencies should ask the accused to prove their innocence instead of harassing the complainants.

If India wants to tackle the corruption menace, it will have to properly educate its anti-corruption investigating officers through rigorous training.

TECHNOLOGY INTERFACE TO TACKLE CORRUPTION

While each State government should have a dedicated complaints monitoring department to handle corruption complaints, such departments should be fully computerized eliminating the need for complainants to meet the government officials who harass them during physical interactions in order to extort bribes from them.

The online interface or “help desk” of the complaints monitoring system should be made available in such a way that the complainants should be able to view the progress of their cases remotely on their computers or mobile devices. The government should take immediate action against the employee if a case gets stuck.

But there are chances of resistance. As most bureaucrats and politicians in India are uneducated or they lack domain expertise, they do not know how to use information technology-based systems such as emails, social media, and video conferencing to deliver citizen services. They also lack communication skills that are required to respond to public complaints over traditional or digital channels. These bureaucrats and politicians shamelessly call common people – including women and senior citizens – to their offices to hear their complaints which are hardly resolved. It is estimated that nearly

one-third of the traffic on roads is of people who go to meet government officials while all these meetings can be avoided by using digital communication channels such as video conferencing. This avoidable traffic is also increasing pollution levels in Indian cities.

While Indian bureaucrats and politicians work like viceroys of the British colonial era, they take sadistic pleasure when people stand outside their offices and bow in front of them. These forced meetings in offices are also increasing corruption which is already rampant in government offices.

The eCommittee of the Supreme Court of India and the Department of Justice (DoJ) of the Government of India have [observed](#) these difficulties that commoners are facing. The eCourts Mission Mode Project – which is a national eGovernance project for technology enablement of courts in the country – encourages the use of digital technology including video conferencing to resolve different cases.

Therefore, the government officials who do not know how to use digital systems to provide government services have no right to call the public to their offices. The government should also terminate the services of such naive officials who cannot keep pace with the modern digital world.

The government must realize that the current online complaint filing systems in all government offices are utterly useless. There is a need to create dynamic digital interfaces where the complainants should be able to monitor the movement of their complaints (along with official remarks) at every stage of their case.

Such interfaces will also increase transparency and reveal the performance of government officials for delivering online citizen services. The government must also understand that the current administrative systems that are supposed to ensure a corruption-free environment are totally dead. There is a need to create a new system of governance to check corruption. The sooner the better. Worse, after arbitrarily closing an unresolved case, the dishonest government officials show it as a resolved case in their records and the government shamelessly claims that the case is resolved.

On the Centralized Public Grievance Redress And Monitoring System ([CPGRAMS](#)) of the Government of India, for example, the government [claims](#) that nearly 60 lakh public grievances were redressed in the period 2022-2024. This is an utter falsehood. The government has not addressed even a fraction of the complaints that it received. The same type of fraud is happening on the other online complaint filing and monitoring

systems of the government while there is no accountability of the government officials for their dereliction of duty.

In the case of Delhi Government, for instance, the Public Grievance Monitoring System (PGMS) and the LG Listening Post service are so crude that they hardly address the public grievances including corruption complaints. These systems are managed by unqualified and mostly corrupt employees who do not give proper response to the public and close the cases without any relief to the complainants. [You can [click here](#) to read a related case study.]

Since the grievances of citizens are not addressed properly, they are left with no other option but to go to courts. But most of them do not get justice in courts which are buried under millions of cases that are pending. As administration has collapsed and courts give haphazard judgments, the lawlessness is increasing rapidly in India.

REASONS FOR INCREASING CORRUPTION IN INDIA

These are some of the reasons because of which corruption is increasing exponentially in India. Weak and Complicated Laws. Unskilled Law-Enforcement Officers. Faulty Complaint Handling Mechanism. Archaic Administrative Systems. Bureaucratic Inefficiency. Limited Use of Technology. Unfortunately, however, there is no organization which is working to overcome all these challenges. As a result, corruption is spreading like a pandemic disease in India.

With casual letters, the anti-corruption outfits pose all sorts of clerical hurdles to dissuade the complainants instead of prosecuting and punishing the corrupt officials. The anti-corruption agencies should, in fact, act as a substitute to courts and handle the public complaints with a formal investigative process to satisfy the complainants completely instead of closing the cases abruptly.

If the anti-corruption departments have to close a case, they should close it with a “Speaking Order” which has all the reasons for their decision to close the case instead of prosecuting the accused officials. The complainants should be given an opportunity to file their rejoinders and argue their cases in front of the jury.

Then the burden on courts and pendency of court cases will reduce. The workload of courts is increasing because the bureaucrats in government offices are not working

honestly to resolve public complaints. Therefore, the harassed citizens have no other option but to approach the courts. Since courts and judges are overworked, their judgments are either inordinately delayed or lack justice. As a result, the lawlessness is increasing in India.

While all the anti-corruption agencies of India are working lawlessly, the CVC sends a carelessly written standard response to all complaints. I have received dozens of such responses from CVC to different complaints that I have filed over the years.

The corrupt CVC bureaucrats do not even give the contact details of the CVO (Chief Vigilance Officer) where they send the complaint because they want to protect the corrupt officials. And the CVOs never respond and never tell the reason why they have not taken any action on the complaint sent to them by the CVC. The entire process is designed to protect the corrupt officials. As a result of the delinquency of anti-corruption officials, corruption is increasing rapidly in all parts of India.

NEED TO REDEVELOP CORRUPTION PROSECUTION PROCESSES

If the Lokpal, CVC, DoPT, CBI, police, or other departments really want to weed out corruption from the country, they must change their archaic complaints management processes and hire skilled domain experts who have thorough process management and communications skills.

A complainant should be allowed to freely file the complaint in any format - paper or digital - after providing their personal details and authenticating them on a properly built complaints management website of a particular anti-corruption department. The

anti-corruption department must immediately send an acknowledgement to the complainant of the receipt of the complaint along with a registration number.

If required, it should be the responsibility of the department official to convert the complaint into the official format. If a complaint has even the slightest circumstantial or direct evidence of corruption, the department should send a formal notice along with the complaint to the accused official with the direction to respond within 15 days.

A copy of this notice should be sent to the complainant or uploaded on the complaints management website with an alert sent to the complainant on their email or mobile phone. The name and contact of the investigating officer should also be communicated to the complainant explicitly.

If the accused official does not respond as directed or does not give their response explicitly to each and every point mentioned in the complaint, it should be assumed that the official is guilty. Then the department should move forward with the prosecution process without requiring any special sanctions for prosecution. Since corruption is rampant in India, the anti-corruption authorities should always find reasons to prosecute and punish the corrupt officials instead of finding excuses to exonerate them without prosecution.

In the next step, the accused official should be asked to appear for online or physical hearings where the complainant should also be allowed to participate. The complaints management website should be so effective that it should allow the accused officials, complainants, and the investigating officers to monitor each step of the investigation and prosecution.

In order to ensure transparency, the comments of each official or complainant in the entire process lifecycle should be available under the case on the complaints management website. As said before, a case should be closed only with a “Speaking Order” giving all the legal and objective reasons for closing the case without convicting the accused officials.

In the past few years, I have filed dozens of complaints against corrupt officials. But all the cases were closed by the CVC, Lokpal, DoPT, police, etc. without any investigation and without any prosecution. On the government's online Centralized Public Grievance Redress And Monitoring System (CPGRAMS), for example, I have filed 136 complaints up to October 6, 2024.

While the CPGRAMS website shows that it has closed 131 of the 136 complaints and only 5 are pending, the truth is that none of my complaints was addressed and all of them were closed arbitrarily. In some cases, I filed appeals to get my complaints reopened as they were wrongly closed. But my appeals also met the same fate and no complaint was addressed.

The screenshot shows the CPGRAMS dashboard with the following data:

- Total Grievances Registered: 136
- Number of Grievances Pending: 5
- Number of Grievances Closed: 131

The 'List of Grievances' table is as follows:

Sn.	Registration Number	Received Date	Grievance description	Status
1	DUGLVE/2024/0006887	05/08/2024	Legal Affairs >> Advice ...	Case Closed (On 06/08/2024)
2	DOPAT/E/2024/009515B	21/07/2024	Personnel and Training >...	Case Closed (On 14/08/2024)
3	GOVPB/E/2024/0001097	14/06/2024	Complaint Against a Form...	Case Closed (On 20/06/2024)

The Centralized Public Grievance Redress And Monitoring System (CPGRAMS) has closed 131 of the 136 complaints that I have filed up to October 6, 2024. But none of my complaints was addressed and all of them were closed arbitrarily.

The CPGRAMS and other such public interfaces are being run in a fraudulent manner by corrupt officials. But they are not being held accountable for their wrongdoings. The decision to close the case should not be based on whimsical grounds used by the investigating officers or other authorities. And the complainants should be allowed to file their rejoinders and argue the case to convince the authorities to convict the accused officials. If there is any lapse in the investigation or the case is closed arbitrarily, the investigating officer should be held accountable for dereliction of duty and complicity in crime.

Now, the same wrong practice of writing useless letters and closing the cases without following due process is being used by other government departments which are full of corrupt officials. The so-called anti-corruption agencies - which are run by naive officials - are also ineffective. If all these cases are handled honestly, a large number of corrupt bureaucrats and politicians will be jailed. Their number is so big that separate jails will have to be built to imprison them.

10 RECOMMENDATIONS TO COMBAT BUREAUCRATIC AND POLITICAL CORRUPTION

These recommendations are particularly important for an extremely corrupt country such as India. However, these measures can also be applied by other nations which are struggling to weed out corruption.

1. Transparency in Investigations

The investigating agencies should hold investigations of corruption cases transparently and publicly release their findings.

2. Circumstantial Evidence

In the cases of organized white-collar financial crimes such as corruption and money laundering, the actual transaction of bribe money is not visible. Therefore, an investigation must be initiated after the collection of circumstantial evidence to track the flow of money.

3. Harsh Punishment

The corrupt bureaucrats, politicians, and others should be incarcerated in harsh detention camps or concentration camps at remote places instead of sending them to conventional jails where they enjoy luxurious facilities.

4. Imprisonment

The minimum prison sentence for corrupt persons should be 10 years in extremely harsh prison conditions.

5. Court Bail

No bail should be granted by courts to corrupt persons once they are jailed.

6. Rogues' Gallery

The names, photographs, and other details of corrupt persons should be made available publicly through an online rogues' gallery launched by the government.

7. Work After Jail

Corrupt persons should not be allowed to work in any public office after the prison sentence.

8. Recovery of Corruption Money

All the money embezzled in corruption along with heavy interest should be recovered from the corrupt persons and they should remain in the concentration camps until the full money is recovered from them.

9. Grand Corruption Cases

In grand corruption cases, the prosecution should run in international courts because the local courts in most countries are extremely weak or complicit to handle such cases. Politicians should not be allowed to say that the cases against them are politically motivated.

10. Human Right

Corruption-free living should be declared a fundamental human right and local as well as international courts should provide justice free of charge to the victims of corruption through simple processes.

Threats to Me: As a journalist and anti-corruption activist, I have been receiving multiple threats including death [threats](#) from the criminals who want to suppress my voice. The National Human Rights Commission (NHRC) of India had directed the Delhi Police to take action so that I could be protected. The NHRC issued its latest [notice](#) on June 11, 2021 with the direction to the Commissioner of Delhi Police to investigate the matter and file its report. After receiving a perfunctory and false report from the corrupt police officials, the NHRC closed the case and never took action against the police or the culprits.

RMN News Services				
RMN News Service	RMN Digital	RMN Stars	RMN Kids	Small Businesses
Digital Magazines and Microsites				
The Unrest		The Integrity Bulletin		
Electronic Voting Machines		Protests by Farmers		
Recent Representations and Research Reports				
E-Filing on Digital Courts	YouTube Modi Videos	Online RCS Complaints		
Farmers' Rights Petition	Digital Courts	Corruption Research 2023		
Legal Aid System	Amendment to DCS Act	Judicial Reforms		
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Twitter in India	Arbitrary Detention	Copyright Laws		
Manipur Violence	Justice for Wrestlers	Children Education Rights		
Petition to CJI	Human Rights Petition	UN Petition on Punjab Unrest		
India Judicial Research Report 2024: Decline of the Indian Judiciary				

ABOUT THE EDITOR: RAKESH RAMAN

The editor of India Corruption Research Reports Rakesh Raman is a national award-winning [journalist](#) and founder of the humanitarian organization RMN Foundation. Besides working at senior editorial positions with leading media companies, he was writing an exclusive edit-page column regularly for The Financial Express, which is a daily business newspaper of The Indian Express Group.

Nowadays, for the past 12 years, he has been [running](#) his own global news services on multiple news sites. He runs various environment protection, human rights protection, education awareness, and anti-corruption campaigns, and publishes digital magazines and research [reports](#) on different subjects. Earlier, he had been associated with the United Nations (UN) through the United Nations Industrial Development Organization (UNIDO) as a digital media expert to help businesses use technology for brand marketing and business development.

At present, Rakesh is associated with the Varieties of Democracy ([V-Dem](#)) Project as a Country Expert for India to provide expert research inputs on multiple topics pertaining to democracy and governance. The V-Dem Project is managed by V-Dem Institute under the University of Gothenburg, Sweden.

In August 2024, he released a [comprehensive report](#) “*India Judicial Research Report 2024: Decline of the Indian Judiciary*” which discusses various factors that are responsible for the downfall of the Indian judiciary. He has also [launched](#) the Pressed Reporter: humanitarian service to protect journalists and press freedom in the world.

In order to inform the Indian citizens and the global community about the extent of corruption in India, he compiled and [released](#) in October 2023 a comprehensive research report “*India Corruption Research Report 2023 (ICRR 2023)*”. It is the second annual report on corruption in India while the first [report](#) ICRR 2022 was released in October 2022.

He has also been publishing *The Integrity Bulletin* news [magazine](#) since 2018 to cover local and international corruption issues to engage with different stakeholders who are trying to combat corruption in the world. He has been [publishing](#) *The Unrest* news magazine since 2020 to cover economic and political upheavals in the world. He has launched a nationwide [campaign](#) to introduce social democracy in India in order to build

an egalitarian society in which all citizens could enjoy equal rights, opportunities, freedoms, and access to justice. He is [running](#) an editorial section / microsite “Power Play: Lok Sabha Elections in India” to cover the election news, events, and political campaigns.

He has also created an exclusive [editorial section](#) to cover elections and politics in the U.S. In January 2024, he launched a [digital microsite](#) to explain the electronic voting machines (EVM) concerns in Indian elections. He has also been running a comprehensive editorial [service](#) “Rural Resistance: Protests by Farmers in India” to cover farmers’ protests and related issues.

He runs the Pathway platform, which is a growth-centric technology [program](#) to help emerging businesses leapfrog in the increasingly competitive global marketplace. He had set up and managed a free [school](#) for 5 years during 2015-2019 to impart modern education to deserving children at the J.J. Colony of Dwarka, Sector 3, New Delhi. He is also running a nationwide [campaign](#) to save school students of India from directionless education so that students could acquire modern skills that can help them in the job market.

In his anti-corruption activities, he participated in a global [petition](#) led by Germany-based international organization Transparency International to call for the UN General Assembly Special Session against Corruption, UNGASS 2021, to direct all countries to set up central, public registers of beneficial ownership.

In December 2023, he joined a global [campaign](#) that demanded the appointment of a United Nations Special Rapporteur on Democracy. He runs a community-driven anti-corruption social [service](#) “Clean House” to help the residents of Delhi raise their voice against the growing corruption and injustice in housing societies where millions of people suffer because of rampant corruption and lawlessness. He has also [formed](#) an environment protection group called Green Group in New Delhi, which is the most polluted national capital in the world.

As Rakesh has been facing constant [threats](#) including death threats for his editorial and anti-corruption work, the Paris-based international organization Reporters Without Borders ([RSF](#)) that defends freedom of journalists has urged the Indian government to save him from threats and persecution. You can [click here](#) to read his full profile while his contact details are given below.

Circulation of India Corruption Research Report 2024

India Corruption Research Report 2024 has been published by RMN Foundation, which is the humanitarian initiative of RMN News Service. This is the only comprehensive report on corruption in India. Besides its circulation in India, this research report will be shared with the world's top anti-corruption organizations, industry associations, politicians, UN agencies, World Bank, the International Monetary Fund (IMF), World Economic Forum, and others so that they should be cautious about rampant corruption in India before entering into any cultural or business alliance with Indian governments or private entities.

As the founder of RMN Foundation and editor of RMN News Service, I have compiled this report independently without any financial or other support. The readers are urged to express their views about it and offer their suggestions for subsequent reports.

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